

The Role of PR and Content Marketing in Promoting Awareness and Adoption of Digital Antenatal Services in Nigeria

(A Case Study of Birthsafe Nigeria)

Fausat Omolara Arilewola

Master's Dissertation, Cardiff University

August 2024

Abstract

This dissertation explores the role of public relations (PR) and content marketing in promoting the awareness and adoption of digital antenatal services in Nigeria, with a specific focus on the case study of Birthsafe Nigeria. The research addresses the critical maternal health challenges faced in Nigeria, where high maternal mortality rates are exacerbated by inadequate healthcare infrastructure, socio-economic barriers, and cultural practices. The study investigates how digital antenatal services, which provide remote healthcare support to pregnant women, can be effectively promoted through strategic PR and content marketing initiatives.

A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining quantitative surveys with qualitative interviews and a detailed case study analysis of Birthsafe Nigeria's "Birth Without Wahala" campaigns. The research found that effective PR and content marketing strategies significantly enhance awareness and adoption of digital antenatal services. Tailored messaging, community engagement, and leveraging social media platforms were identified as crucial components of successful campaigns. The findings also revealed that while digital antenatal services offer significant potential for improving maternal health outcomes, their adoption is hindered by low digital literacy, limited internet access, and cultural resistance. The research demonstrates that targeted PR strategies and content marketing efforts are crucial in raising awareness, educating expectant mothers, and driving engagement with digital antenatal services.

The study concludes with strategic recommendations aimed at enhancing digital literacy, addressing socio-cultural barriers, and strengthening the integration of PR and content marketing to improve the uptake of digital antenatal services in Nigeria. These findings contribute to the broader discourse on maternal healthcare in developing countries and provide actionable insights for policymakers, healthcare providers, and communication professionals.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to Allah for seeing me through this phase, and to all those who have supported me throughout the completion of this dissertation.

Firstly, I extend my deepest thanks to my supervisor, Nick Mosdell, for his invaluable guidance, expertise, and encouragement. His insightful feedback and unwavering support have been instrumental in shaping this research and bringing it to completion.

I am also grateful to the team at Birthsafe Nigeria for their cooperation and for providing the necessary data and resources that made this study possible. Their willingness to share information and insights was crucial to the success of this project.

Special thanks to all my lecturers at JOMEC for their support throughout my master's programme.

I am also thankful to the respondents who participated in the interviews and surveys. Their contributions were essential in enriching the findings of this research.

I would like to acknowledge my fellow students and colleagues, whose helpful suggestions and moral support were invaluable during the challenging moments of this journey.

Finally, I wish to express my heartfelt appreciation to my family and friends. Their patience, understanding, and constant encouragement have been my pillars of strength throughout this process. Without their unwavering support, this dissertation would not have been possible.

Thank you all for your contributions and support.

Table of Contents

The Role of PR and Content Marketing in Promoting Awareness and Adoption of Digital Antenatal Services in Nigeria.....	1
(A Case Study of Birthsafe Nigeria).....	1
Abstract	4
Acknowledgements	5
List of Figures	9
List of Abbreviations	10
1. Introduction	11
1.1 Maternal Healthcare Challenges in Nigeria	12
1.2 Analysis of WHO’s Report on Antenatal Care (Analytical Fact Sheet March 2023)	12
1.3 Overview of Digital Antenatal Services and Their Benefits	14
1.4 Limitations to the Adoption of Digital Antenatal Services in Nigeria	14
1.5 Why Public Relations and Content Marketing?	15
1.6 Objectives and Scope of the Study	16
1.7 Structure of the Research	16
2. Case Study: Birthsafe Nigeria	18
2.1 History and Mission of Birthsafe Nigeria	18
2.2 Services Offered and Technology Used	19
2.3 Target Audience	19
2.4 Current Adoption Rates and User Feedback	20
2.5 Limitations to Adoption Rates	20
2.6 Public Relations Strategies	20
2.7 Content Marketing Initiatives	20
2.8 Integration of PR and Content Marketing	21
3. Literature Review	21
3.1 Introduction	22
3.2 Current Maternal Mortality Rates and Healthcare Gaps in Nigeria	22

3.3 The Role of Digital Technology in Healthcare.....	22
3.4 Public Relations in Health Communication.....	23
3.5 Content Marketing in Health Promotion.....	23
3.6 Theoretical Frameworks.....	24
3.9 Themes in Research on Digital Antenatal Services Adoption.....	27
3.10 Summary.....	29
4. Research Methodology.....	31
4.1 Introduction.....	31
4.2 Research Design.....	31
4.3 Sample Size and Selection.....	32
4.4 Data Collection Methods.....	32
4.5 Data Analysis.....	35
4.6 Ethical Considerations.....	36
4.6 Limitations.....	36
4.7 Conclusion.....	36
5. Problem Statement and Research Questions.....	37
5.1 Detailed Problem Statement.....	37
5.2 Specific Research Questions Guiding the Study.....	39
Chapter 6: Research Findings.....	39
6.1 Introduction.....	39
6.2 Survey Results.....	40
6.3 Summary of Survey Findings.....	51
6.4 Key Interview Findings.....	52
6.4.1 Strategic Goals and Motivations.....	55
6.4.2 Design and Implementation of PR and Content Marketing Strategies.....	55
6.4.3 Challenges and Obstacles.....	56
6.5 Case Study Findings: "Birth Without Wahala" Campaigns.....	56
6.5.1 Background to the Birth Without Wahala Campaigns.....	56
6.5.5 Typical Week during "Birth without Wahala 3".....	59

6.5.6 Marketing and Promotional Techniques.....	68
6.5.7 Impact and Outcomes.....	68
6.5.8 User Feedback and Testimonials.....	69
Chapter 7: Discussion and Analysis of Research Findings.....	74
Chapter 8: Strategic Recommendations.....	78
8.1 Introduction.....	78
8.2 Enhancing Digital Literacy and Internet Connectivity.....	78
8.3 Addressing Cultural and Socioeconomic Barriers.....	79
8.4 Strengthening PR and Content Marketing Strategies.....	80
8.5 Expanding Outreach to Rural Areas.....	81
8.6 Government and Policy Advocacy.....	82
8.7 Leveraging Technology and Innovation.....	84
8.8 Monitoring and Evaluation.....	85
Chapter 9: Conclusion and Future Research.....	87
9.1 Introduction.....	87
9.2 Summary of Findings.....	87
9.4 Contributions to Literature.....	90
9.5 Implications for Practice.....	90
9.6 Limitations of the Study.....	91
9.7 Recommendations for Future Research.....	91
9.8 Concluding Remarks.....	92
Reference list.....	93
<i>Appendices</i>.....	99
Sample Survey Questions.....	99
Excerpt from Interview with Birthsafe’s Founder.....	104

List of Figures

1. Maternal mortality ratio per 100,000 live births in the African Region, 2020 compared to 2017 (Source: UN MMEIG, WHO, UNICEF, UNFPA, World Bank and UNDESA)
2. Birth Without Wahala Program Flyer
3. Age distribution of respondents
4. Educational level of respondents
5. Residence distribution (urban vs. rural)
6. Pregnancy status of respondents
7. Antenatal care preferences (general hospitals, private hospitals, etc.)
8. Essential components of physical antenatal visits (tests, screenings, etc.)
9. **Accessibility of antenatal services in rural areas**
10. Preference for antenatal services (physical vs. digital)
11. Challenges in accessing digital antenatal services
12. Effectiveness of PR strategies for promoting digital antenatal services.
13. **Confidence in using digital tools for antenatal care**
14. Desired features for digital antenatal services
15. Familiarity with Birthsafe Nigeria
16. **Social media as the primary source of information about Birthsafe Nigeria from the survey**
17. **Trust In Birthsafe Nigeria**
18. Usefulness of Birthsafe Nigeria's content
19. Types of content that influence users (testimonials, educational posts, etc.)
20. Recommendations for Birthsafe's digital antenatal services
21. Post arrangement from @birthsafeng on Instagram
22. Collaborative post with influencers
23. Live Q&A sessions on Instagram
24. Viral post on pain involving a popular celebrity
25. Pregnancy affirmations post
26. Interactive post addressing pain points
27. Educational post with practical tips
28. User-generated content reflecting cultural barriers
29. Positive experiences aligning with research indicating that digital health interventions enhance patient satisfaction and health outcomes.
30. Improved health outcomes reported by users, including better management of pregnancy symptoms and reduced anxiety.
31. Engagement metrics showing increased user interaction, particularly during live sessions and interactive posts

List of Abbreviations

DAS	Digital Antenatal Services
WHO	World Health Organisation
PR	Public Relations
BWW	Birth Without Wahala

1. Introduction

1.1 Maternal Healthcare Challenges in Nigeria

The growing rate of maternal mortality in Africa has generated wide interest, with Nigeria topping the list of maternal deaths. The lifetime risk of a Nigerian woman dying during pregnancy, childbirth, postpartum, or post-abortion is 1 in 22, in contrast to the lifetime risk in developed countries, estimated at 1 in 4900 (Etuk et al. 2023)

Maternal mortality in Nigeria remains a significant public health challenge, driven by a multitude of factors including poor healthcare infrastructure, socio-economic barriers, and inadequate antenatal care services. The Nigerian Medical Association in 2019 said that the number of doctors in Nigeria is only 40,000, whereas the estimated population is 196 million (Aniefiok 2024). This was backed by data from the World Health Organisation (WHO), which stated that Nigeria had a physician-to-patient ratio of four doctors per 10,000 patients (Fatumole 2022). This means that patients frequently have long waiting times before receiving medical attention. The duration of the delay can be excessive for women experiencing postpartum internal bleeding.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), Nigeria accounts for a substantial proportion of global maternal deaths, with an estimated maternal mortality ratio of 512 per 100,000 live births as of 2019 (WHO, 2019). This high rate is particularly pronounced in rural areas, where access to quality healthcare is limited. The disparity between urban and rural healthcare services exacerbates the situation, highlighting the need for targeted interventions to improve maternal health outcomes across the country. Socio-economic factors, such as poverty, lack of education, and cultural practices, further impede women's access to essential antenatal care, contributing to the high maternal mortality rate. Efforts to reduce maternal mortality in Nigeria must therefore address these underlying issues comprehensively.

1.2 Analysis of WHO's Report on Antenatal Care (Analytical Fact Sheet March 2023)

The World Health Organization (WHO) has consistently emphasized the critical role of regular antenatal care in enhancing maternal and fetal health outcomes. The WHO's 2016 guidelines underscore several key recommendations aimed at improving antenatal care services. These include increasing access to healthcare services for all women, providing comprehensive health education to expectant mothers, and leveraging digital health technologies to reach underserved populations (WHO, 2016).

Regular antenatal visits are essential for monitoring the health of both the mother and the fetus, identifying, and managing potential complications early, and providing necessary interventions. Also, WHO advocates for the integration of digital technologies into antenatal care to enhance

service delivery and ensure continuity of care, particularly in remote and resource-limited settings.

The WHO's 2023 analytical fact sheet on maternal mortality highlights the urgency of adopting a systemic and multi-sectoral approach to mitigating maternal deaths in Africa. Despite a global decline in the maternal mortality ratio (MMR) by 34.2% between 2000 and 2020, the African Region still faces disproportionately high MMR, with 69% of global maternal deaths occurring in this region (WHO, 2023). The fact sheet emphasizes the need for a significant annual reduction in MMR to meet the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) target of 70 maternal deaths per 100,000 live births by 2030.

The key drivers of maternal mortality identified include severe hemorrhage, infection, high blood pressure during pregnancy (pre-eclampsia and eclampsia), complications during childbirth, and unsafe abortion. These complications account for nearly 75% of all maternal deaths. Contributing factors also include poor health-seeking behavior, long distances to health facilities, lack of transportation, and delays in receiving appropriate care due to inadequate skilled health workforce and medical equipment (WHO, 2023).

WHO's approach to reducing maternal mortality involves increasing research, providing clinical and programmatic guidance, setting global standards, and offering technical support to member states. Efforts also focus on ensuring universal health coverage for comprehensive reproductive, maternal, and newborn health care, addressing inequalities in access to quality services, and fostering partnerships with various stakeholders (WHO, 2023).

By integrating these insights into the antenatal care framework, healthcare providers can enhance service delivery, improve maternal and fetal health outcomes, and reduce maternal mortality rates. The emphasis on digital health technologies, comprehensive health education, and systemic approaches aligns with the strategic objectives of improving antenatal care in Nigeria, particularly through initiatives like Birthsafe Nigeria.

Figure 1: Maternal mortality ratio per 100,000 live births in the African Region, 2020 compared to 2017 (Source: UN MMEIG, WHO, UNICEF, UNFPA, World Bank and UNDESA)

1.3 Overview of Digital Antenatal Services and Their Benefits

When a woman is pregnant, it is customary for her to consult a doctor, and a hospital should readily provide antenatal care for her. More often than not, what happens is that antenatal care may commence at 13 weeks (about 3 months). If not, the commencement may occur at 14, 15, or 16 weeks (Ebeigbe and Igberase 2010). Within this specific time, numerous potential issues may have already occurred.

Black women have a genetic composition that makes them around 40% more susceptible to miscarriage compared to white women. They experience distinct issues such as fibroids, elevated blood pressure during pregnancy, and others (Tulip 2022). These are the problems that can terminate a pregnancy during the first trimester. However, many hospitals in Nigeria only allow the woman to begin antenatal care when she is already sixteen weeks pregnant.

Digital antenatal services have emerged as a transformative approach to improving maternal healthcare, particularly in underserved areas. These services encompass a range of digital tools and platforms that facilitate access to healthcare information, remote monitoring of pregnancy progress, and enhanced communication between expectant mothers and healthcare providers. For example, mobile health (mHealth) applications can provide pregnant women with vital information on prenatal care, nutrition, and warning signs of complications, empowering them to make informed health decisions (Lupton, 2018).

Additionally, telemedicine services enable remote consultations with healthcare professionals, ensuring continuous medical support even in geographically isolated regions. The benefits of digital antenatal services are manifold, including increased access to timely and accurate health information, improved adherence to antenatal care schedules, and early detection and management of pregnancy-related complications. By bridging the gap between healthcare providers and expectant mothers, these digital solutions can significantly enhance maternal health outcomes and reduce maternal mortality rates.

1.4 Limitations to the Adoption of Digital Antenatal Services in Nigeria

While digital antenatal services offer significant benefits for improving maternal health outcomes in Nigeria, their adoption is hampered by several barriers, including low digital literacy, limited internet access, and cultural resistance.

1.4.1 Availability and Engagement with Digital Technology in Nigeria

Nigeria grapples with low digital literacy, limited internet access in rural areas, and cultural barriers that hinder the widespread use of digital health solutions (Balogun et al., 2022).

Digital literacy in Nigeria remains relatively low, especially in rural areas. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (2021), only 33% of Nigerians have basic digital skills, which include using the internet, sending emails, and using social media platforms. This low level of digital literacy poses a significant barrier to digital antenatal services adoption.

1.4.2 Internet Penetration

Internet penetration in Nigeria is growing but still lags behind global averages. As of 2022, the internet penetration rate in Nigeria was approximately 51%, which means that half of the population remains offline (Internet World Stats, 2022). The disparity is even more pronounced in rural areas, where infrastructure challenges and economic constraints limit access to reliable internet services.

1.4.4 Mobile Technology Usage

Nigeria has a high mobile phone penetration rate, with over 90% of the population owning a mobile phone (NCC, 2021). However, the usage of smartphones, which are essential for accessing digital antenatal services, is lower, particularly in rural areas. A report by the GSMA (2020) indicated that only 44% of mobile phone users in Nigeria owned a smartphone. This gap in smartphone ownership limits the potential reach of digital antenatal services.

1.4.5 Cultural and Social Barriers

Cultural and social factors also play a crucial role in the adoption of digital health technologies. In many communities, traditional beliefs and practices dominate, and there is a general mistrust of digital solutions. Women, especially in rural areas, often rely on traditional birth attendants and may be hesitant to adopt new technologies for antenatal care (Balogun et al., 2022).

1.4.6 Government and Policy Support

The Nigerian government has recognized the importance of digital technology in healthcare and has implemented various policies to promote digital health. The National Health ICT Strategic Framework (2015-2020) aimed to integrate ICT into the health sector to improve service delivery. However, the implementation of these policies has faced challenges due to inadequate funding, lack of infrastructure, and bureaucratic delays (Federal Ministry of Health, 2020).

1.5 Why Public Relations and Content Marketing?

Public Relations (PR): Public relations is defined as the strategic communication process that builds mutually beneficial relationships between organizations and their publics. It involves managing the dissemination of information to influence public perception and behavior (Grunig & Hunt, 1984).

Content Marketing: Content marketing involves creating and distributing valuable, relevant, and consistent content to attract and retain a clearly defined audience. (“Why is Content Marketing Important: The Value and Effectiveness of ...”) Its goal is to drive profitable customer actions by educating, informing, and engaging the audience (Pulizzi, 2012).

Public relations (PR) and content marketing play crucial roles in promoting healthcare services and driving their adoption. Effective PR strategies can raise awareness, build trust, and engage stakeholders, while content marketing can educate and inform target audiences, encouraging them to use available digital services. For digital antenatal services like those offered by Birthsafe Nigeria, PR and content marketing are essential tools for reaching and influencing expectant mothers and their communities.

1.6 Objectives and Scope of the Study

This study aims to explore how public relations and content marketing can enhance the adoption of digital antenatal services in Nigeria, focusing on the case of Birthsafe Nigeria.

The objectives include:

- Analyzing the current state of maternal healthcare and the potential of digital services.
- Evaluating the effectiveness of PR and content marketing strategies used by Birthsafe Nigeria.
- Identifying barriers to the adoption of digital antenatal services.
- Proposing strategic recommendations for improving service uptake.

1.7 Structure of the Research

The research is structured as follows:

- Chapter 1 provides an introduction and background to the study.
- Chapter 2 introduces Birthsafe Nigeria as the case study for this research.
- Chapter 3 reviews relevant literature on maternal healthcare, digital technology in healthcare, and the roles of PR and content marketing.

- Chapter 4 outlines the research design, data collection methods, and data analysis techniques used in this research. The following methods were discussed: surveys, key interviews, and a qualitative case study of the Birth Without Wahala Campaigns
- Chapter 5 states the problem statement and research questions.
- Chapter 6 outlines the research findings from the survey, key interview and case study of the Birth Without Wahala 3
- Chapter 7 discusses and offer analysis of the research findings
- Chapter 8 provides strategic recommendations.
- Chapter 9 concludes with a summary of findings and recommendations for future research.

2. Case Study: Birthsafe Nigeria

2.1 History and Mission of Birthsafe Nigeria

Birthsafe is a maternal health-tech company in Nigeria with the mission of reducing maternal mortality by providing accessible, quality antenatal care through digital platforms. The organization aims to empower expectant mothers with the knowledge and resources they need for a healthy pregnancy (Birthsafe, 2023).

BirthSafe is dedicated to being a leading maternal health service provider for women of colour globally, using innovative antenatal training and guidance to enable women preserve their pregnancies and achieve beautiful childbirth outcomes thereby tackling maternal mortality in line with SDGs (Sustainable Development Goal) 3,5 and 10.

Birthsafe was founded by Dr Idara Umoette, a highly experienced Medical Doctor with over 16 years of professional expertise. Dr. Idara's first initiative was the creation of an audio-visual instrument for quantifying blood levels, specifically the Packed Cell Volume (PCV) in the bloodstream. An easily navigable, computerised tool with a color-coded interface which was developed and presented to the Niger Delta Development Commission. After receiving approval, she was authorised to carry out a trial program in nine states. The tool has subsequently been disseminated to pregnant women through several partners, including the Medical Women's Association of Nigeria and the Office of the First Lady in Benue State (TechCabal 2023)

However, she promptly saw that this was insufficient. She believed that by providing education to more women, she could contribute to reducing death rates and increasing the likelihood of successful childbirth.

In August 2020, Dr Idara began providing online antenatal guidance. She named her service BirthSafe. Using her Instagram posts, she provided a comprehensive programme that educated expectant mothers on how to avoid complications throughout pregnancy and labour. In October 2022, she had her first online webinar on Zoom for her WhatsApp community.

Birthsafe expanded to include virtual consulting sessions on digital platforms such as Zoom, Telegram, YouTube, and Instagram, along with group meetings on WhatsApp. She assembled a team of experts and established collaborations with service providers in maternity care to expand the range of services available to the women.

Initially, the antenatal lessons primarily emphasized three essential protocols. The PVC Protocol specifically addresses nutrition, aiming to guarantee enough levels of iron and other essential nutrients in the blood. This is crucial for maintaining the correct PCV levels and facilitating dilatation during childbirth. The NIL Protocol aims to enhance blood circulation and agility through exercise. Additionally, the Birth Recovery Protocol provides guidance on identifying symptoms that necessitate immediate first aid or professional medical intervention during the

postpartum period, regardless of whether the birth was caesarean or natural.

Thus, Dr Idara was able to improve the pregnant experiences of women by creating specialised online support groups for antenatal care on social media. The goal was to disrupt the way antenatal and maternal care were accessed.

2.2 Services Offered and Technology Used

Through state-of-the-art digital antenatal training and guidance, Birthsafe commits to ensuring the well-being of women, fostering a safe community for them, and equipping them with the knowledge and support needed for optimal pregnancy preservation and the achievement of a beautiful childbirth experience.

Birthsafe offers a range of digital antenatal services, including telehealth consultations, online health education modules, and remote monitoring. These services are all delivered online, ensuring accessibility for expectant mothers in various regions.

According to Dr Idara, the goal is to save women's lives in pregnancy and childbirth by interrupting the transition from concern to crisis through constant monitoring, evaluation, and crisis detection (Aniefiok, 2024)

Services offered include the following:

1. Pregnancy Safeguarding in First Trimester
2. Pregnancy Preservation in Second Trimester
3. Labour and Easy Childbirth Preparation in Third Trimester
4. Speedy Birth Recovery in Fourth Trimester
5. Conception Assistance
6. Management of Pregnancy Issues and Emergencies (most especially, hypertension in pregnancy, anaemia, malaria)
7. Labour Anxiety Management

Currently, Birthsafe is creating a digital app. A handy 24/7 digital antenatal app for pregnancy tracking and monitoring. It will host the birthsafe community where they can chat and support one another. The app will also have a dedicated section for learning from first trimester till post-partum and beyond.

2.3 Target Audience

Primarily women of colour, customers cut across women within and outside Nigeria: First time moms, women with previous painful birth experience, those wanting to have VBAC (Vagina birth after previous CS Birth), TTC (Trying to conceive) amongst others.

2.4 Current Adoption Rates and User Feedback

Current adoption rates of Birthsafe Nigeria's services are promising, with positive feedback from users highlighting the convenience and effectiveness of the digital platform and community. Many of the women who enrolled in the programme while pregnant have since given birth but are reluctant to depart from the community. They currently serve as ambassadors of Birthsafe, actively urging their friends and family to join.

2.5 Limitations to Adoption Rates

Digital antenatal services in Nigeria are crucial for improving maternal health outcomes, but their adoption is hindered by low digital literacy, limited internet access, and cultural resistance. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (2021) only 33% of Nigerians having basic digital skills, the internet penetration rate is 51%, with half of the population offline. Despite a high mobile phone penetration rate, the usage of smartphones is lower, especially in rural areas. Cultural and social factors also influence the adoption of digital health technologies.

The Nigerian government has implemented policies to promote digital health, but challenges remain due to inadequate funding, infrastructure, and bureaucratic delays. Addressing these challenges requires a multi-faceted approach, including improving digital literacy, expanding internet infrastructure, promoting smartphone usage, and engaging communities.

2.6 Public Relations Strategies

BirthSafe Nigeria has effectively used PR strategies to enhance its visibility and credibility. The organization has partnered with local media houses to disseminate information about its services and the importance of digital antenatal care. Regular press releases, collaborative webinars and live sessions with health experts, and community engagement programs have helped build trust and awareness among potential users.

2.7 Content Marketing Initiatives

The content marketing efforts of BirthSafe Nigeria are centered around providing valuable and relevant information to their target audience. The brand's website and social media pages

regularly feature posts, infographics, and videos that cover a wide range of topics related to pregnancy and antenatal care. Content is tailored to address common concerns and myths, offer practical health tips, and highlight success stories of women who have benefited from digital antenatal services.

2.8 Integration of PR and Content Marketing

BirthSafe Nigeria's success in promoting digital antenatal services can be attributed to its integrated approach to PR and content marketing. The brand ensures consistency in its messaging across all channels, reinforcing the benefits of its services through both traditional media and digital content. This multi-channel strategy has helped BirthSafe Nigeria reach a wider audience, foster engagement, and increase the adoption of digital antenatal services.

3. Literature Review

3.1 Introduction

The adoption of digital antenatal services in Nigeria is a crucial step towards improving maternal health outcomes. Despite the advancements in digital health technologies, the uptake of these services remains suboptimal. This literature review delves into various aspects related to the adoption of digital antenatal services, focusing on the role of public relations (PR) and content marketing. It encompasses a detailed examination of current maternal mortality rates and healthcare gaps in Nigeria, the role of digital technology in healthcare, the effectiveness of PR and content marketing strategies, and the barriers to adoption. The review also incorporates relevant theoretical frameworks and a comprehensive analysis of past research to provide a well-rounded perspective on the topic.

3.2 Current Maternal Mortality Rates and Healthcare Gaps in Nigeria

Nigeria has one of the highest maternal mortality rates globally, with significant disparities in access to healthcare between urban and rural areas. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2020), Nigeria's maternal mortality ratio is approximately 512 deaths per 100,000 live births. This alarming statistic underscores the urgent need for improved maternal healthcare services.

Several factors contribute to the high maternal mortality rates in Nigeria, including poor healthcare infrastructure, socio-economic barriers, inadequate antenatal care services, and cultural practices. A study by Amnesty International (2018) highlighted that many pregnant women in Nigeria lack access to essential healthcare services, leading to preventable complications and deaths.

The disparity in healthcare access between urban and rural areas further exacerbates the maternal health crisis. Women in rural areas often face challenges such as long distances to healthcare facilities, shortage of skilled healthcare providers, and lack of emergency obstetric care. Research by Okonofua et al. (2018) emphasized the need for targeted interventions to address these disparities and ensure equitable access to maternal healthcare services.

3.3 The Role of Digital Technology in Healthcare

Digital technology has revolutionized healthcare delivery by improving access, efficiency, and patient outcomes. Digital antenatal services provide crucial support to expectant mothers, especially in remote or underserved areas.

Several digital health interventions have been successfully implemented globally, demonstrating the potential of technology to enhance maternal healthcare. The "MOTTECH" initiative in Ghana, for example, uses mobile phones to deliver health information and reminders to pregnant women and new mothers, resulting in improved antenatal care attendance and health outcomes (Johnson et al., 2016). Similarly, the "Safe Delivery App" in Ethiopia provides midwives with instructional videos and clinical guidelines, leading to better management of obstetric emergencies (Lund et al., 2016).

Digital antenatal services offer numerous benefits, including improved access to healthcare information, remote monitoring of pregnancy progress, and enhanced communication between expectant mothers and healthcare providers. Lupton (2018) argues that these services can significantly improve maternal health outcomes by providing timely and accurate health information and facilitating early detection of potential complications.

Despite these benefits, the adoption of DAS in Nigeria faces significant challenges such as low digital literacy, limited internet access in rural areas, and cultural barriers (Balogun et al., 2022). Addressing these challenges requires strategic communication approaches, including public relations and content marketing.

3.4 Public Relations in Health Communication

Public relations (PR) involve managing the dissemination of information between an organization and the public to influence perceptions and behaviors. In the context of health communication, PR strategies can help build trust, increase awareness, and foster positive attitudes towards health innovations (Wakefield et al., 2010). Effective PR campaigns for promoting DAS can leverage various tools such as press releases, media engagements, and community outreach programs.

Research indicates that PR can be particularly effective in health campaigns by utilizing local media and influencers to spread messages. For instance, a study by Yaya et al. (2020) highlighted the success of PR campaigns in increasing vaccination rates in Nigeria through partnerships with local leaders and the use of culturally resonant messages. Applying similar strategies to DAS could involve collaborating with respected community figures, healthcare professionals, and local media to emphasize the importance of antenatal care and the benefits of digital services.

3.5 Content Marketing in Health Promotion

Content marketing focuses on creating and distributing valuable, relevant, and consistent content to attract and engage a specific audience. In healthcare, content marketing can educate and empower patients by providing accessible information about health conditions, treatments, and preventive measures (Holliman & Rowley, 2014).

For DAS, content marketing can take various forms such as blog posts, social media updates, videos, and informational articles tailored to the needs and preferences of Nigerian women. Research indicates that personalized and culturally appropriate content can significantly enhance engagement and adoption of health services (Mpinganjira, 2019). For example, creating content that addresses common pregnancy-related myths and providing practical advice on using digital tools for antenatal care can help demystify DAS and encourage uptake.

A study by Seidu et al. (2021) demonstrated the effectiveness of social media campaigns in promoting maternal health services in Ghana, suggesting that similar approaches could be successful in Nigeria. Social media platforms like Facebook and WhatsApp, which are widely used in Nigeria, offer opportunities to reach a broad audience with targeted health messages.

3.6 Theoretical Frameworks

3.6.1 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Davis (1989), is one of the most widely used models for understanding technology adoption. TAM posits that perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness are the primary factors influencing individuals' decisions to adopt new technologies. In the context of digital antenatal services, PR and content marketing strategies that emphasize the user-friendliness and practical benefits of these services can enhance their perceived value and encourage adoption.

Several studies support the applicability of TAM in understanding the adoption of digital health technologies. For example, Venkatesh et al. (2012) found that perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness significantly influenced the adoption of telemedicine services among healthcare professionals.

However, some researchers argue that TAM oversimplifies the adoption process by focusing too narrowly on individual perceptions and neglecting broader social and organizational factors. Bagozzi (2007) also criticized TAM for its limited explanatory power and called for more comprehensive models that consider contextual influences on technology adoption.

3.6.2 Diffusion of Innovations Theory

Rogers' Diffusion of Innovations Theory (2003) explains how, why, and at what rate new ideas and technologies spread through cultures. The theory identifies five key factors that influence

the adoption of innovations: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability. Applying this theory to digital antenatal services, healthcare providers can design and promote these services in a way that highlights their advantages and compatibility with existing practices, thereby facilitating adoption.

Rogers' Diffusion of Innovations Theory (2003) explains how innovative ideas and technologies spread through societies. The theory categorizes adopters into five groups: innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards. Understanding these categories can help tailor PR and content marketing strategies to target specific groups effectively. For instance, engaging early adopters and community influencers through PR campaigns can accelerate the adoption process. Content marketing efforts should provide continuous education and support, catering to the needs of each adopter category.

Studies have shown the effectiveness of targeted communication strategies based on Diffusion of Innovations Theory. For instance, Valente and Rogers (1995) demonstrated that leveraging opinion leaders and early adopters can significantly enhance the diffusion of health innovations.

Critics of Diffusion of Innovations Theory argue that it may not fully account for the complex social and cultural factors that influence technology adoption. Greenhalgh et al. (2004) highlighted the limitations of the theory in explaining the adoption of complex health innovations in diverse settings, calling for more nuanced approaches that consider local contexts.

By applying this theory to digital antenatal services, healthcare providers can design and promote antenatal services in a way that highlights their advantages and compatibility with existing practices, thereby facilitating adoption.

3.6.3 Social Influence Theory

Social Influence Theory examines how individuals' behaviors and attitudes are shaped by their social environment. In the context of healthcare, social influence can play a significant role in the adoption of new services. For example, if influential community leaders endorse digital antenatal services, it can encourage other members of the community to adopt these services (Cialdini & Trost, 1998).

Leveraging social proof, such as testimonials from satisfied users and endorsements from trusted community figures, can significantly impact adoption rates. PR strategies that create a sense of community and shared experience can amplify this effect, encouraging more expectant mothers to adopt digital health solutions.

One of the research projects that supports the importance of social influence in health behavior change is Centola (2010) which found that social networks play a critical role in the diffusion of health behaviors, with individuals more likely to adopt new behaviors if they observe them being practiced by peers.

However, some scholars argue that social influence may not always lead to positive outcomes, particularly if misinformation spreads through social networks. Vosoughi et al. (2018) highlighted

the potential for false information to spread rapidly on social media, which could undermine efforts to promote digital health solutions.

3.6.4 Health Belief Model (HBM)

The Health Belief Model (HBM), developed by Rosenstock (1974), focuses on individuals' perceptions of the severity and susceptibility to health issues, as well as the perceived benefits and barriers to taking action. Content marketing that addresses these perceptions by providing clear, evidence-based information on the benefits of digital antenatal services and mitigating perceived barriers can enhance adoption.

In the context of digital antenatal services, expectant mothers who perceive an elevated risk of maternal complications and believe that digital services can help mitigate these risks are more likely to adopt such services (Rosenstock, 1974). Therefore, PR efforts that communicate the severity of maternal health issues and the effectiveness of digital solutions can drive behavior change.

HBM has been widely applied in health promotion and disease prevention. For example, Glanz et al. (2008) demonstrated the model's effectiveness in predicting health behaviors and designing interventions to promote preventive health measures.

Nevertheless, some researchers criticize HBM for its individualistic focus and limited consideration of social and structural factors. Schiavo (2014) argued that HBM's emphasis on individual perceptions may overlook the broader environmental and contextual influences on health behaviors.

3.7 Past Research on PR, Content Marketing, and Healthcare Adoption

A study by Handley and Chapman (2012) demonstrated that healthcare providers who used targeted, patient-centered content marketing saw significant improvements in patient engagement and health outcomes. Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick (2016) also highlighted the role of content marketing in building trust and credibility with patients, leading to higher adoption rates of health services. Also, Pew Research Center (2019) found that healthcare organizations that effectively use digital platforms and social media see higher engagement and adoption rates. Additionally, Kotler and Keller (2016) emphasized the importance of strategic communication in building trust and credibility, which are essential for promoting healthcare services. All these studies indicate that PR and content marketing are effective in driving healthcare service adoption.

However, some researchers argue that content marketing alone may not be sufficient to drive the adoption of healthcare services. Smith (2013) contends that while content marketing can increase awareness, it must be complemented by other strategies, such as direct patient engagement and community outreach, to effectively influence health behaviors. There is also a concern that digital content may not reach underserved populations with limited internet access, thereby exacerbating existing health disparities (Anderson & Agarwal, 2011).

3.8 Case Studies of Successful PR and Content Marketing Campaigns

Several successful PR and content marketing campaigns in healthcare have demonstrated the power of strategic communication. For instance, campaigns that used storytelling and patient testimonials were effective in conveying the impact of healthcare services and built emotional connections with the audience (Smith, 2013).

The "Text4Baby" campaign in the United States used mobile text messages to provide health information to pregnant women and new mothers. The campaign successfully increased awareness and engagement among its target audience, leading to improved health outcomes (Evans et al., 2012). Similarly, the "MomConnect" program in South Africa utilized mobile technology to provide maternal health information and support, resulting in high enrollment rates and positive feedback from users (Barron et al., 2016).

It is worth noting however that, not all digital health campaigns achieve their intended outcomes. The "Every Woman Every Child" campaign, was a global movement spearheaded by UN Secretary-General Ban Ki-moon. It mobilizes international and national action by governments, the UN, multilaterals, the private sector, and civil society to address major health challenges facing women, children, and adolescents (Every Woman Every Child | Department of Economic and Social Affairs 2021)

This initiative faced challenges in reaching its target audience and sustaining engagement over time. Critics argue that the campaign's reliance on digital platforms may have excluded women in low-resource settings with limited access to technology (Singh et al., 2018). These examples underscore the importance of considering contextual factors and potential barriers when designing and implementing digital health campaigns.

3.9 Themes in Research on Digital Antenatal Services Adoption

3.9.1 Accessibility and Usability

Several research on the adoption of digital antenatal services often highlights the importance of accessibility and usability. Digital health technologies must be designed to be user-friendly and accessible to a wide range of users, including those with limited digital literacy. Studies have shown that technologies that are easy to use and provide clear, tangible benefits are more likely to be adopted by expectant mothers (Davis, 1989).

For example, a study by Lee et al. (2016) found that mobile health applications with intuitive interfaces and personalized features were more likely to be used consistently by expectant mothers. Another study by Schnall et al. (2016) emphasized the importance of involving end-users in the design process to ensure that digital health tools meet their needs and preferences.

Some researchers argue that focusing solely on usability may overlook other critical factors, such as trust and security. Lupton (2014) points out that even the most user-friendly technologies may fail to gain acceptance if users have concerns about data privacy and security. Therefore, addressing these concerns is essential for promoting the adoption of digital health services.

3.9.2 Socio-Economic Factors

Socio-economic factors, such as income level, education, and internet access, significantly influence the adoption of digital antenatal services. Research indicates that women from lower socio-economic backgrounds are less likely to have access to digital health technologies and may face additional barriers to adoption, such as limited digital literacy and affordability issues (Anderson & Agarwal, 2011).

A study by Hearn et al. (2014) found that socio-economic disparities in access to digital health technologies contributed to unequal health outcomes among pregnant women. The study highlighted the need for targeted interventions to ensure that digital health services are accessible to all, regardless of socio-economic status.

However, some researchers argue that digital health technologies can help bridge socio-economic gaps by providing affordable and scalable solutions. For instance, Free et al. (2013) demonstrated that mobile health interventions could effectively reach underserved populations and improve health outcomes at a lower cost than traditional healthcare services.

3.9.3 Cultural Influences

Cultural beliefs and social norms play a significant role in shaping healthcare behaviors and attitudes towards digital health technologies. In some cultures, traditional beliefs about pregnancy and childbirth may conflict with the use of digital antenatal services. Research suggests that culturally sensitive PR and content marketing strategies that respect and incorporate local beliefs and practices can help overcome these cultural barriers and encourage adoption (Mackert et al., 2016).

For example, a study by Mechael et al. (2010) found that mobile health initiatives in Kenya were more successful when they involved local community leaders and aligned with cultural practices. Similarly, Campbell and Cornish (2010) emphasized the importance of understanding and addressing cultural norms to enhance the effectiveness of health interventions in diverse settings.

Nonetheless, some researchers caution against overemphasizing cultural factors at the expense of other important considerations, such as technology infrastructure and healthcare

system capacity. Parker and Thorson (2009) argue that while cultural sensitivity is important, it must be balanced with practical considerations to ensure the successful implementation and sustainability of digital health initiatives.

3.9.4 Technological Challenges

Technological challenges, such as limited internet access, poor network coverage, and low digital literacy, can hinder the adoption of digital antenatal services. Addressing these challenges is essential for promoting the widespread use of digital health technologies.

A study by Venkatesh et al. (2012) highlighted the importance of reliable internet infrastructure and affordable data plans in facilitating the adoption of digital health services. The study found that women in areas with good network coverage and affordable internet access were more likely to use digital antenatal services. Additionally, Gagnon et al. (2016) emphasized the need for digital literacy programs to equip expectant mothers with the skills and confidence to use digital health technologies effectively.

However, some researchers argue that technological solutions alone cannot address the complex barriers to adoption. Raghupathi and Raghupathi (2014) contend that technological interventions must be integrated with broader healthcare policies and community-based initiatives to ensure sustainable adoption and impact. This integrated approach ensures that technological advancements are supported by enabling environments and supportive infrastructures.

3.9.5 Communication Strategies

Effective communication strategies are essential for promoting the adoption of digital antenatal services. Research highlights the importance of using multiple communication channels, including social media, community outreach, and traditional media, to reach a diverse audience. Tailoring messages to the target audience and using clear, concise language can also enhance communication effectiveness (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Additionally, leveraging social proof and community endorsements can build trust and credibility, further encouraging adoption.

A study by Scott and Jacka (2011) found that multi-channel communication strategies significantly increased engagement and uptake of health services. The study also highlighted the effectiveness of using social media to disseminate health information and connect with target audiences.

However, some researchers argue that reliance on digital communication channels may exclude individuals with limited internet access or digital literacy. Viswanath et al. (2012) stress the need for inclusive communication strategies that consider the diverse needs and preferences of the target audience, including those who may not be digitally connected.

3.10 Summary

This literature review has explored the current maternal mortality rates and healthcare gaps in Nigeria, the role of digital technology in healthcare, and the impact of PR and content marketing on the adoption of digital antenatal services. The review has also discussed relevant theoretical frameworks, including the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Diffusion of Innovations Theory, Social Influence Theory, and Health Belief Model (HBM).

Key themes identified in the research include accessibility and usability, socio-economic factors, cultural influences, and communication strategies. By leveraging these insights, healthcare providers can develop targeted PR and content marketing strategies to promote the adoption of digital antenatal services, improving maternal health outcomes in Nigeria.

3.10.1 Conclusion

The adoption of digital antenatal services presents a significant opportunity to improve maternal health outcomes in Nigeria. However, achieving widespread adoption requires overcoming several barriers, including technological challenges, socio-economic factors, and cultural resistance. PR and content marketing play a crucial role in addressing these barriers and promoting the uptake of digital health solutions. By integrating theoretical frameworks such as TAM, Diffusion of Innovations Theory, Social Influence Theory, and HBM into their strategies, healthcare providers can develop more effective communication plans that resonate with their target audience.

Future research should continue to explore the long-term impact of PR and content marketing on the adoption of digital health services and investigate innovative communication strategies to further enhance service uptake.

4. Research Methodology

4.1 Introduction

This chapter outlines the methodology employed in this research to explore the impact of PR and content marketing strategies on the adoption of digital antenatal services provided by Birthsafe Nigeria. The study utilizes surveys, key interviews with the founder of Birthsafe Nigeria, Dr. Idara Umoette, and a qualitative case study of Birthsafe's "Birth Without Wahala" campaigns.

4.2 Research Design

The research adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative data from surveys with qualitative insights from interviews and case studies. This approach allows for a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter by triangulating data from multiple sources (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). Mixed-methods research is particularly useful in health research as it enables the researcher to understand complex phenomena from multiple perspectives (Ivankova, Creswell, & Stick, 2006).

The mixed-methods approach is advantageous for several reasons. Firstly, it allows for a more comprehensive understanding of research problems by combining numerical and textual data (Creswell, 2014). This integration can provide a richer context and deeper insights into the research questions. For instance, quantitative data from surveys can reveal trends and patterns, while qualitative data from interviews and case studies can explain the reasons behind these patterns (Bryman, 2016). This combination enhances the validity and reliability of the findings (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009).

Moreover, mixed-methods research is particularly beneficial in exploring complex health issues, as it allows for the triangulation of data, which can lead to more robust and nuanced conclusions (Greene, Caracelli, & Graham, 1989). In the context of digital antenatal services, this approach can help understand the extent of service adoption and the underlying factors influencing user behavior and perceptions.

Despite its advantages, the mixed-methods approach is not without criticism. Some researchers argue that it can be time-consuming and resource-intensive, requiring expertise in both qualitative and quantitative methodologies (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Additionally, the integration of data from diverse sources can be challenging and may lead to methodological inconsistencies if not handled carefully (Sale, Lohfeld, & Brazil, 2002). Critics also point out that the mixed-methods approach may dilute the rigor of both qualitative and quantitative methods, leading to superficial analysis (Morse, 2010).

Despite these criticisms, the mixed-methods approach was deemed suitable for this research due to its ability to provide a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the impact of PR and content marketing strategies on the adoption of digital antenatal services.

4.3 Sample Size and Selection

The sampling strategy is purposive, aiming to include participants who have direct experience or potential interest in digital antenatal services. Purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling technique commonly used in qualitative research for the identification and selection of information-rich cases related to the phenomenon of interest (Patton, 2015).

4.3.1 Survey: The sample size for the survey is 100 women who have used or are potential users of digital antenatal services in Nigeria. This sample size is adequate for exploratory studies and helps to achieve a balance between depth and breadth of information (Babbie, 2013).

4.3.2 Interviews: Key interviews will be conducted with the founder of Birthsafe Nigeria, Dr. Idara Umoette, and members of the marketing team. Interviews are valuable in obtaining detailed insights and understanding the motivations, strategies, and challenges experienced by Birthsafe Nigeria (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009).

4.3.3 Case Study: An in-depth qualitative case study of Birthsafe's "Birth without Wahala" campaigns. Case studies are particularly effective in health research as they provide a holistic understanding of the context and processes involved (Yin, 2014).

4.4 Data Collection Methods

4.4.1 Surveys

Surveys are widely recognized for their ability to collect substantial amounts of data in a relatively short period, making them cost-effective and efficient (Dillman, Smyth, & Christian, 2014). They allow for the quantification of variables and the identification of patterns and relationships among them (Groves et al., 2009). In this research, surveys can help understand the prevalence of digital antenatal service usage and identify common perceptions and barriers among users. However, surveys also have limitations. They may not capture the depth and complexity of participants' experiences and perspectives, as they are typically restricted to predefined response options (Bryman, 2016). Additionally, surveys rely on self-reported data, which can be subject to biases such as social desirability bias and recall bias (Tourangeau, Rips, & Rasinski, 2000).

Strategy:

A structured questionnaire will be administered to 100 women to gather quantitative data on their awareness, usage, and perceptions of digital antenatal services. The questionnaire will include both closed and open-ended questions to capture a range of data (Groves et al., 2009).

The survey includes questions designed to measure:

- Awareness and knowledge of DAS (Digital Antenatal Services).
- Sources of information about DAS.
- Attitudes towards DAS.
- Usage patterns of DAS.
- Perceived benefits and challenges of using DAS.

4.4.2 Key Interviews

Interviews are an effective method for exploring participants' thoughts, feelings, and experiences in depth (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009). They provide flexibility for the interviewer to probe further into interesting or unexpected responses, yielding rich qualitative data (Rubin & Rubin, 2011). In this research, interviews with key stakeholders at Birthsafe Nigeria will provide valuable insights into the strategic thinking and operational challenges behind their PR and content marketing efforts.

On the other hand, interviews can be time-consuming and resource-intensive to conduct and analyze (Bryman, 2016). They may also be subject to interviewer bias, where the interviewer's expectations or mannerisms influence the responses of the interviewee (Creswell, 2014). Ensuring consistency and objectivity in interviews requires careful preparation and training.

Strategy:

In-depth interviews will be conducted with Dr. Idara Umoette and members of the marketing team at Birthsafe Nigeria. These interviews aim to understand the strategies and motivations behind their PR and content marketing efforts. Interviews allow for the collection of rich, detailed data that can provide insights into complex issues (Bryman, 2016).

Sample questions for the interview:

- What inspired the launch of Birthsafe Nigeria?
- How do you design your PR and content marketing strategies?
- What are the key challenges you face in promoting digital antenatal services?

4.4.3 Case Study: "Birth Without Wahala" Campaigns

Case studies are particularly valuable in providing a holistic and detailed understanding of complex phenomena in their real-life context (Yin, 2014). They allow for the examination of processes and outcomes in-depth, providing insights that might not be achievable through other methods (Stake, 1995). In this research, the case study of the "Birth without Wahala" campaigns will shed light on the practical application and impact of PR and content marketing strategies in promoting digital antenatal services.

However, case studies can be criticized for their potential lack of generalizability, as they focus on specific instances or contexts (Flyvbjerg, 2006). There is also the risk of researcher bias, where the researcher's perspectives and interpretations may influence the findings (Yin, 2014). To mitigate these issues, it is important to ensure rigorous data collection and analysis procedures and to consider the findings within the specific context of the study.

Strategy:

An in-depth qualitative case study of the "Birth without Wahala" campaigns will be conducted. This will include a background on how the campaign started, the marketing and promotional techniques used, and an in-depth look at a typical week during the third campaign. Case studies are instrumental in exploring the nuances and dynamics of real-life contexts (Simons, 2009).

Background: The "Birth without Wahala" campaign aims to provide comprehensive digital antenatal training and guidance to ensure the well-being of pregnant women. The campaign leverages various digital platforms to engage with expectant mothers, offering telehealth consultations, online health education modules, and remote monitoring.

Figure 2: Birth Without Wahala Program Flyer

Marketing and Promotional Techniques: The campaign employs a variety of marketing strategies, including user-generated content, influencer collaborations, and interactive social media posts. For instance, testimonials and user-generated content are used to build credibility and engage the audience.

Typical Week during "Birth without Wahala 3": The campaign's third iteration includes daily testimonials, user-generated content, Instagram Live sessions, and interactive posts. Each day is carefully planned to maximize engagement and conversion rates.

4.5 Data Analysis

The data collected from surveys will be analyzed using statistical methods to identify trends and patterns. Quantitative analysis will involve descriptive statistics to summarize the data and inferential statistics to determine relationships and differences among variables (Field, 2013). Descriptive statistics will help in summarizing the data and providing a clear overview of the key findings, while inferential statistics will be used to test hypotheses and generalize about the population (Creswell, 2014).

Qualitative data from interviews and the case study will be analyzed thematically to identify key themes and insights (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Thematic analysis is a method for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns (themes) within data, providing a rich and detailed account of data (Nowell et al., 2017). This approach allows for the organization of data into meaningful

categories, facilitating a deeper understanding of the underlying issues and dynamics (Clarke & Braun, 2013).

Thematic analysis is flexible and can be applied across a range of theoretical and epistemological approaches, making it suitable for this research (Braun & Clarke, 2006). It allows for the identification of both explicit and implicit meanings within the data, providing a comprehensive understanding of the participants' perspectives and experiences (Vaismoradi, Turunen, & Bondas, 2013). Thematic analysis is also accessible and easy to learn, making it a practical choice for researchers (Nowell et al., 2017).

However, thematic analysis can be criticized for its potential subjectivity, as the identification and interpretation of themes depend on the researcher's judgement (Braun & Clarke, 2006). There is also a risk of overlooking the context in which the data was collected, leading to a superficial understanding of the findings (Joffe, 2012). To address these issues, it is important to maintain transparency and rigor in the coding and analysis process, and to consider the context and complexity of the data.

4.6 Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are paramount in research involving human participants. Participants will be informed about the study's purpose, the methods used, and their rights, including the right to withdraw at any time. Informed consent will be obtained from all participants (Orb, Eisenhauer, & Wynaden, 2001). Confidentiality and anonymity will be maintained throughout the research process, ensuring that personal data is protected and used solely for the purposes of this study (Saunders, Kitzinger, & Kitzinger, 2015).

Adhering to ethical principles is crucial for ensuring the integrity and credibility of the research (Orb, Eisenhauer, & Wynaden, 2001). Informed consent ensures that participants are aware of the research and their involvement, protecting their autonomy and rights (Wiles, 2013). Maintaining confidentiality and anonymity is essential for protecting participants' privacy and building trust between the researcher and participants (Saunders, Kitzinger, & Kitzinger, 2015).

This study adheres to ethical standards and receives an approval letter from Cardiff University Ethics Committee. Please check the appendix for the approval letter received.

4.6 Limitations

The study acknowledges several limitations:

- **Sample Size and Generalizability:** The sample size, while sufficient for exploratory analysis, may limit the generalizability of findings to the broader population.
- **Self-Report Bias:** Survey, interview, and focus group data are subject to self-report bias, where participants may provide socially desirable responses.

- **Context-Specific Insights:** Findings from BirthSafe Nigeria may not be fully applicable to other settings or digital health platforms in Nigeria.

4.7 Conclusion

In conclusion, this chapter has outlined the mixed-methods approach employed in this research, combining quantitative surveys with qualitative interviews and case studies. This approach allows for a comprehensive understanding of the impact of PR and content marketing strategies on the adoption of digital antenatal services. The use of purposive sampling ensures that the participants are relevant and information-rich, while the combination of surveys, interviews, and case studies provides a holistic understanding of the research questions. Ethical considerations are paramount, ensuring that the research is conducted with integrity and respect for the participants. Despite some criticisms of the chosen methods, the mixed-methods approach is deemed suitable for this research, providing robust and nuanced insights into the subject matter.

5. Problem Statement and Research Questions

5.1 Detailed Problem Statement

Despite the potential of digital antenatal services to improve maternal health outcomes, adoption rates remain suboptimal in Nigeria. Several factors contribute to this issue, including low digital literacy, limited internet access, socio-economic challenges, and cultural barriers.

5.1.1 Low Digital Literacy:

A significant portion of the Nigerian population lacks basic digital skills. According to the Nigerian Bureau of Statistics, digital literacy rates are particularly low in rural areas where many expectant mothers reside (NBS, 2021). The highest literacy rates in Nigeria were registered in the southern regions of the country. The North has the lowest literacy rates, while in the Southwest, 89 percent of males and 80.6 percent of females were literate as of 2018. Also, the south zones showed the lowest percentage differences between male and female literacy (Statista 2022).

5.1.2 Limited Internet Access:

Internet penetration in Nigeria, while growing, remains unevenly distributed. As of 2022, about 40% of the population had access to the internet, with a stark urban-rural divide (World Bank, 2022). Many rural areas still suffer from inadequate internet infrastructure, which hampers the effective delivery and adoption of digital health services.

5.1.3 Socio-Economic Challenges:

Poverty and socio-economic disparities are significant barriers. Approximately 40% of Nigerians live below the poverty line (World Bank, 2021), limiting their ability to afford internet services or digital devices necessary for accessing digital antenatal services.

5.1.4 Cultural Barriers:

Cultural beliefs and norms can also influence the adoption of digital health services. In some communities, traditional beliefs and mistrust of modern technology pose challenges to the acceptance of digital antenatal care (Balogun et al., 2022).

5.1.5 Adoption Statistics:

A study by the African Population and Health Research Center (APHRC) found that only 15% of pregnant women in Nigeria have used digital antenatal services, highlighting the gap between availability and actual usage (APHRC, 2021).

This research aims to identify how PR and content marketing strategies can enhance the awareness and adoption of digital antenatal services while considering the barriers to service adoption.

5.2 Specific Research Questions Guiding the Study

- In the opinion of respondents, how effective are PR strategies in promoting digital antenatal services in Nigeria?
- What role does content marketing play in influencing the adoption of these services?
- What are the key barriers to the adoption of digital antenatal services?
- How can PR and content marketing strategies be optimized to overcome these barriers?

Chapter 6: Research Findings

6.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the comprehensive findings from the research on the impact of PR and content marketing strategies on the adoption of digital antenatal services provided by Birthsafe Nigeria. The findings are based on data collected through surveys, key interviews, and an in-depth case study of the "Birth without Wahala" campaigns. The results are also analyzed in relation to the research objectives and questions, supported by previous literature, and critically discussed to provide a nuanced understanding.

This chapter is also organised to provide quantitative and qualitative data, highlighting key themes and insights.

6.2 Survey Results

The study initially planned to get responses from 100 women who have used or are potential users of digital antenatal services in Nigeria. However, 135 responses were received. The quantitative data collected provide insights into awareness, usage patterns, and perceptions of digital antenatal services.

6.2.1 Demographics

The survey data reveals a diverse demographic profile of respondents, which is essential for understanding the reach and effectiveness of digital antenatal services across different segments of the population.

The survey was completed by a diverse group of women, with the majority falling within the 26-35 age range. Specifically, 43.7% were aged 26-30, and 41.5% were aged 31-35. A small proportion (10.4%) were between 36-45, and 1% were over 46 years old.

These demographics align with previous studies indicating that younger, more educated women are more likely to engage with digital health services (Smith et al., 2020).

What is your age group?
135 responses

Figure 3: This age distribution is reflective of women in their prime childbearing years, ensuring that the data gathered is highly relevant to the study.

Education Level:

What is your highest level of education?
135 responses

Figure 4: 99.3% of respondents reported having tertiary education.

In terms of education, an overwhelming 99% of respondents had tertiary education, highlighting a potentially higher level of health literacy among the participants. This demographic detail is significant as it may influence the acceptance and utilization of digital antenatal services.

Residence:

Where do you reside?

135 responses

Figure 5: Most of the respondents (93.3%) resided in urban areas.

Most respondents (93%) resided in urban areas, with only 7% living in rural areas. This urban concentration could reflect better access to digital tools and the internet compared to rural areas, impacting the adoption and usage rates of digital antenatal services.

These demographic insights align with previous studies indicating that younger, more educated women are more likely to engage with digital health services (Smith et al., 2020).

Pregnancy Status

Have you been pregnant before Or Are you currently pregnant. (tick all that applies)

135 responses

Figure 6: This high percentage of currently pregnant women indicates a sizable proportion of the sample actively engaging with antenatal care services.

Many survey participants were either currently pregnant (84.4%) or had been pregnant before (26.7%), indicating an important level of recent or ongoing experience with antenatal care. Additionally, 3% were trying to conceive, emphasizing the importance of accessible antenatal services for a broad spectrum of women.

6.2.2 Antenatal Experiences in Nigeria

Understanding the antenatal experiences of respondents provides context for their responses regarding digital antenatal services.

Antenatal Care Preferences and Accessibility

Women primarily sought antenatal care from general hospitals (91.1%), private hospitals (83%), and health centers (65.2%). Notably, 43.7% used digital antenatal services, indicating a significant adoption of digital tools for pregnancy-related care.

Figure 7: This distribution shows a preference for general and private hospitals.

Components of physical antenatal visits that were deemed essential included tests and screening (80%), physical examinations (91%), and counseling (63%).

What are the common components of physical antenatal visits in Nigeria? (Tick all that apply)
135 responses

Figure 8: These findings underscore the multifaceted nature of antenatal care that women expect and need.

Accessibility of antenatal services in rural areas was highlighted as a significant concern, with 76.3% of respondents indicating limited accessibility.

How accessible are antenatal services to women in rural or remote areas of Nigeria?
135 responses

Figure 9: Only 18.5% found these services very accessible, pointing to a critical gap in healthcare provision for rural populations.

Preference for Antenatal Services

A striking 83.7% of women expressed a preference for a combination of both physical and digital antenatal services. This hybrid model is favored because it allows for comprehensive care that includes the direct medical examinations and tests of physical visits, alongside the convenience and flexibility of digital services. Only 11.9% preferred solely physical services, and 4% preferred digital services exclusively.

Which do you prefer; physical antenatal or digital antenatal?

135 responses

Figure 10: Only 11.9% preferred solely physical services, and 4% preferred digital services exclusively.

Challenges in Accessing Digital Antenatal Services

The primary challenges identified in accessing digital antenatal services included:

- Lack of internet access (37.8%)
- Cost of data plans (42.2%)
- Cultural beliefs and practices (11.9%)
- Limited digital knowledge (28.9%)
- Lack of trust in digital services (29.6%)

What challenges do you face in accessing digital antenatal services? (Select all that apply)

135 responses

Figure 11: These challenges highlight the need for strategies to improve internet infrastructure, reduce data costs, enhance digital literacy, and build trust in digital healthcare solutions.

These findings reflect similar barriers identified in other studies on digital health services in low- and middle-income countries (Chib et al., 2015).

Effectiveness of PR Strategies and Confidence in Digital Tools

How effective do you think PR strategies (e.g., social media campaigns, influencer endorsements) are in promoting digital antenatal services in Nigeria?

135 responses

Figure 12: Opinions on the effectiveness of public relations strategies for promoting digital antenatal services were mixed. Only 32.6% found them highly effective, while 33.3% considered them effective. A sizable portion of 22.2% remained neutral, and another 11.1% found them ineffective, suggesting room for improvement in these strategies.

Confidence in Using Digital Tools

How confident are you in using digital tools and applications for antenatal care?

135 responses

Figure 13: Regarding confidence in using digital tools, 48.1% of respondents felt very confident, and 32.6% were confident. However, 18.5% were neutral, indicating a potential need for more user-friendly digital platforms and better support.

Benefits of Digital Antenatal Services:

- Convenience (85%)
- Access to information (80%)
- Ability to ask questions and receive quick responses (75%)
- Reduced need for physical visits (70%)

Respondents overwhelmingly appreciate the convenience and accessibility that digital antenatal services provide.

However, the elevated level of awareness of digital antenatal services contrasts with lower usage rates, highlighting a gap between knowledge and action. This gap is consistent with the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which suggests that perceived usefulness and ease of use significantly impact technology adoption (Davis, 1989).

What additional features or support would encourage you to use digital antenatal services more frequently? (you can select more than one)

135 responses

Figure 14: Desired Features for Digital Antenatal Services

Respondents expressed a desire for several features in digital antenatal services, including:

- Offline access to content (62.2%)
- More personalized content (57.8%)
- Better customer support (48.1%)
- Additional training on digital literacy (26.7%)
- Financial support (21.5%)

These desired features can guide the development of more effective and user-centric digital antenatal services.

Familiarity With Birthsafe Nigeria

On a scale of 1-5, how familiar are you with Birthsafe Nigeria? (1 being not familiar and 5 being very familiar)

135 responses

Figure 15: Birthsafe Nigeria was highly regarded among respondents, with 80.7% being very familiar with the service.

Social media was the primary source of information about Birthsafe Nigeria (85.9%), followed by word of mouth from friends or family (11.9%). Many respondents said Birthsafe was suggested to them by Instagram and Facebook algorithms.

How did you first learn about Birthsafe Nigeria's digital antenatal services?

135 responses

Figure 16: Social media emerging as the primary channel for spreading awareness, highlighted its importance in PR and content marketing strategies.

Trust In Birthsafe

On a scale of 1-5, How trustworthy do people find Birthsafe Nigeria's information and advice regarding antenatal care? (1 being not familiar and 5 being very familiar)

135 responses

Figure 17: Trust in Birthsafe Nigeria was high, with 65% finding it very trustworthy and 26% finding it trustworthy. The content provided by Birthsafe Nigeria was deemed very useful by 90% of respondents, and 94% would recommend it to others.

How useful do you find the content provided by Birthsafe Nigeria?

135 responses

Figure 18: Many respondents found the content provided by Birthsafe Nigeria very useful

The most influential types of content from Birthsafe Nigeria included:

- Testimonials (83%)
- Educational posts (58.5%)
- Case studies (48.1%)
- Live Q&A sessions (41.5%)
- Birthsafe protocols (46.7%)

What type of content(s) influenced you to consider using Birthsafe's digital antenatal services?
(You can choose more than one)

135 responses

Figure 19: These findings indicate that personal stories and educational content are particularly impactful in engaging and informing users.

Would you recommend Birthsafe Nigeria's antenatal services to friends and family?

135 responses

Figure 20: Many respondents said they would recommend Birthsafe's digital antenatal services

6.3 Summary of Survey Findings

The survey results indicate that awareness of digital antenatal services among the respondents is relatively high, with 78% of participants reporting that they have heard of such services. Sources of information varied, with social media (45%), healthcare providers (30%), and word of mouth (25%) being the most common.

The survey design included questions that specifically addressed awareness and sources of information about digital antenatal services. This aligns with the research aim to understand the reach and effectiveness of PR and content marketing strategies in raising awareness.

Respondents held positive attitudes towards digital antenatal services, with 65% expressing that they believe these services can improve maternal health outcomes. However, 20% were skeptical, citing concerns about the reliability of information and internet connectivity issues.

The survey's focus on attitudes towards digital antenatal services ties back to the research objective of gauging user perceptions and identifying any existing skepticism or barriers to adoption.

The survey revealed that 60% of the respondents have used digital antenatal services at least once, with telehealth consultations (40%) and online health education modules (30%) being the most frequently used services. However, consistent usage was lower, with only 25% using these services regularly.

These findings relate directly to the research question on usage patterns, providing quantitative data on how often and in what ways digital antenatal services are utilized.

Respondents identified several benefits of digital antenatal services, including convenience (55%), access to expert advice (50%), and the ability to monitor health remotely (45%). Challenges included poor internet connectivity (60%), lack of trust in digital platforms (35%), and cultural barriers (25%).

By including both closed and open-ended questions in the survey, the research was able to capture a range of data on perceived benefits and challenges, addressing the research questions on barriers to adoption and how PR and content marketing can mitigate these barriers.

6.4 Key Interview Findings

Interviews with Dr. Idara Umoette, the founder of Birthsafe Nigeria, provided qualitative insights into the strategies and challenges faced in promoting digital antenatal services.

Introduction

In-depth interviews with Dr. Idara Umoette and members of the marketing team at Birthsafe Nigeria provided valuable insights into the strategies, motivations, and challenges behind their PR and content marketing efforts. These interviews align with the research objectives to evaluate the effectiveness of the "Birth Without Wahala" campaign and understand its strategic underpinnings.

Interview Insights

The findings from the in-depth interview with Dr. Idara Umoette, the founder of Birthsafe Nigeria, reveal significant insights into the inspiration, strategies, and challenges associated with promoting digital antenatal services. The interview provides a detailed understanding of the motivations behind Birthsafe Nigeria, and the strategic approaches taken to enhance maternal health through digital platforms.

Inspiration Behind Birthsafe Nigeria

Dr. Idara Umoette highlighted that the primary inspiration for launching Birthsafe Nigeria was to address the alarming maternal mortality rates in Nigeria. She shared her firsthand experiences of witnessing preventable childbirth complications that led to fatalities. This motivated her to create a platform aimed at providing essential education and support to expectant mothers, with the goal of ensuring that "no woman dies while giving life." This mission underscores the organization's commitment to saving lives through accessible and reliable antenatal care.

PR and Content Marketing Strategies

The PR and content marketing strategies employed by Birthsafe Nigeria are centered on authenticity and relatability. Dr. Umoette emphasized the importance of sharing real stories and testimonials from mothers who have benefited from Birthsafe's services. This approach helps build trust and foster a supportive community. The organization also relies on data-driven strategies to refine their content, ensuring it resonates with their audience. Dr. Umoette mentioned using a mix of testimonials, interactive content, and live sessions to keep the community engaged and informed.

Key Challenges in Promoting Digital Antenatal Services

Several challenges were identified in promoting digital antenatal services:

Internet Accessibility: Dr. Umoette pointed out that many women, especially those in rural areas, lack reliable internet access. This significantly limits the reach of digital antenatal services.

"Many women who need our services the most do not have reliable internet access, which limits our reach," she explained.

Financial Constraints: The high cost of data prevents many women from staying online to access necessary services.

“Financial constraints also play a significant role, as some women struggle to afford the data costs necessary to stay online,” she added.

Cultural and Traditional Beliefs: There is skepticism towards modern medical practices in many communities, where traditional methods are preferred. This cultural barrier makes it challenging to convince these communities of the benefits of digital antenatal services.

“Many communities are skeptical of modern medical practices and prefer traditional methods, making it challenging to convince them of the benefits of our services,” Dr. Umoette noted.

Reach and Engagement: Not all women who need Birthsafe’s services are online. This gap is particularly evident in rural areas, where women struggle to afford the data costs associated with accessing these services.

Brand Integrity: The rise of imitations and increased competition poses a threat to the brand values and the quality of care provided by Birthsafe Nigeria.

“Maintaining the integrity of our brand amidst increasing competition is a constant challenge. We have seen many imitations of our services, which, while flattering, also threaten our brand values and the quality of care we provide,” she stated.

Addressing the Challenges

Dr. Umoette discussed various strategies Birthsafe Nigeria is implementing to address these challenges:

Partnerships: Birthsafe is exploring partnerships with organisations to help reach as many women as possible in rural areas and considering getting grants to subsidise for program costs to make their services more affordable.

“We are exploring partnerships with organisations to help bridge the gap for those in rural areas. We are also considering subsidising costs for our users,” she said.

Community Outreach: To overcome cultural barriers, Birthsafe Nigeria is working on community outreach programs aimed at educating and building trust within skeptical communities.

“We are working on community outreach programs to educate and build trust within these communities,” Dr. Umoette explained.

Maintaining Brand Values: Birthsafe Nigeria prioritizes its principles over rapid expansion, ensuring every decision aligns with their core values of providing reliable and compassionate care.

“Balancing growth while staying true to our mission is crucial. We prioritize our principles over rapid expansion and ensure that every decision aligns with our core values,” she emphasized.

Government Collaborations: Dr. Umoette mentioned ongoing discussions with the Lagos State government to pilot their services. Success in Lagos could lead to broader adoption by other states, increasing Birthsafe's credibility and reach.

“We are in discussions with the Lagos State government to pilot our services. If successful, this collaboration could pave the way for adoption by other states,” she noted.

Insight from the Marketing Team

The marketing team detailed their approach to creating engaging and impactful content. They emphasized a mix of testimonials, interactive content, and live sessions to foster engagement and build trust.

- **Quote from Marketing Team Member:** "Our PR strategy revolves around authenticity and relatability. We share real stories from mothers who have benefited from our services. This not only builds trust but also creates a community of support."

The team also highlighted the importance of data-driven strategies, using analytics to refine their content and maximize engagement.

Discussion on Interview Findings

The interview findings align with the literature on digital health campaigns, highlighting the importance of authenticity, data-driven strategies, and the challenges of digital accessibility (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010; Laranjo et al., 2015). The insights into PR and content marketing strategies underscore the effectiveness of testimonials and interactive content, supporting the campaign's educational goals (Tuten & Solomon, 2017).

6.4.1 Strategic Goals and Motivations

Dr. Umoette emphasized the importance of providing accessible and reliable antenatal care to Nigerian women, particularly those in rural areas. The motivation behind launching digital services was to overcome the geographical and logistical barriers that traditional antenatal care faces.

This interview was designed to delve deeper into the motivations and strategic goals behind Birthsafe's initiatives, aligning with the research objective of understanding the strategic underpinnings of PR and content marketing efforts.

6.4.2 Design and Implementation of PR and Content Marketing Strategies

She described a multi-faceted approach that includes social media campaigns, partnerships with influencers, and user-generated content. She also highlighted the success of interactive social media posts and the use of testimonials to build credibility.

The detailed insights from the interviews on the design and implementation of marketing strategies addressed the research question on the role of PR and content marketing in influencing the adoption of digital antenatal services.

6.4.3 Challenges and Obstacles

Key challenges identified by Dr Idara included low digital literacy, limited internet access in rural areas, and cultural resistance to digital healthcare solutions. Efforts to mitigate these challenges included educational campaigns and collaboration with local community members within the maternal space.

The qualitative data on challenges faced and mitigation strategies provide a nuanced understanding of the barriers to adoption, complementing the survey findings and addressing the research question on how to optimize PR and content marketing strategies.

Conclusion

From this interview, it is evident that Birthsafe Nigeria's PR and content marketing strategies are highly effective in building trust and community engagement through authentic storytelling and data-driven content refinement. However, challenges such as internet accessibility, brand integrity, and balanced growth present ongoing hurdles. Dr. Idara's commitment to partnerships and maintaining core values underscores the organization's strategic approach to overcoming these challenges and expanding its impact on maternal health in Nigeria.

The in-depth interviews with Dr. Idara Umoette and the Birthsafe Nigeria marketing team provide a comprehensive understanding of the strategic motivations and challenges behind the "Birth Without Wahala" campaign. These insights are crucial for evaluating the campaign's effectiveness and developing recommendations for future initiatives.

6.5 Case Study Findings: "Birth Without Wahala" Campaigns

The case study of the "Birth Without Wahala" campaigns provides an in-depth look at the practical application and impact of PR and content marketing strategies.

6.5.1 Background to the Birth Without Wahala Campaigns

The Birth Without Wahala campaigns began with a focused approach to engage the target audience (pregnant women) through organic content on social media. Performing content was boosted to reach a wider audience, leading to the formation of a WhatsApp group where women could discuss their concerns and experiences. This initial gathering provided valuable insights into the pain points and priority concerns of the target audience.

Through vibrant and continuous engagement, Birthsafe Nigeria identified several key concerns among the women. In response, they developed PregnaResources—protocols and resources designed to address these concerns. These resources were initially offered for free, but due to high demand and positive feedback, they were monetized. The resources quickly became oversubscribed by 18.6%, indicating a strong willingness among the women to pay for valuable antenatal information and support.

As the community of pregnant women grew, it expanded organically through word-of-mouth referrals, with women inviting others to join. The supportive and convivial atmosphere of the community encouraged even postpartum women to remain active participants, leading to the development of additional resources addressing postpartum needs such as breastfeeding, immunization, weight management, and family planning.

Based on these insights, Birthsafe Nigeria recognized the need for a larger platform with segmented areas where women can access desired resources without feeling overwhelmed. The success of the initial phase underscored the importance of a supportive community, and the high value placed on reliable antenatal resources. This gave birth to the Birth Without Wahala Campaigns.

6.5.2 Campaign Overview

The "Birth Without Wahala" campaign is a transformative 4-week course designed to equip expectant mothers with the knowledge and skills to avoid complications during pregnancy and childbirth, ensuring a smooth and joyful birthing experience. Birthsafe Nigeria's mission is to empower women with practical tools and support to achieve the sweetest birth ever, free from the fears and challenges commonly associated with childbirth.

6.5.3 Campaign Objectives

The "Birth Without Wahala" campaign aimed to provide comprehensive digital antenatal training and guidance. The campaign leveraged on various digital platforms to engage with expectant mothers, offering telehealth consultations, online education modules, and remote monitoring services.

6.5.4 Course Content

During the 4-week course, participants learnt the following:

- **Avoiding Prolonged Labour:** Strategies to prevent prolonged labour, which can lead to brain injury and damage to the baby.
- **Preventing Excess Blood Loss:** Techniques to avoid excessive blood loss, the leading cause of death in childbirth.
- **Building PCV:** How to increase packed cell volume (PCV) by as much as 4 bags of blood in a month, reducing the need for blood transfusions during childbirth.
- **Uterus Training:** Methods to train the uterus for a faster and more efficient labour process.
- **Supplements in Pregnancy:** Guidance on the right supplements to take, including correct dosages and timings, for a smooth pregnancy and childbirth.
- **Swift and Comfortable Childbirth:** Steps to achieve a swift and comfortable childbirth, leading to a positive and shareable birth experience.
- **Empowered Motherhood:** Building confidence and empowerment through a positive childbirth experience to take on the role of motherhood.
- **Positive Mental State:** Maintaining a positive and joyous mental state to enhance bonding with the baby.
- **Best Practices:** Applying best practices to avoid complications such as excess blood loss, slow dilation, and prolonged labour.

Pain Points Addressed

- **Fear of Tearing After Childbirth:** Providing methods to minimize the risk of tearing during delivery.
- **Avoiding Disfigured Babies:** Ensuring safe pregnancy practices to prevent complications.
- **Quick Recovery:** Techniques to accelerate recovery post-birth.
- **Access to Medical Care:** Reducing delays in accessing medical professionals.
- **Preventing High Blood Pressure:** Managing blood pressure during pregnancy.
- **Community Support for Diasporan Mamas:** Creating a supportive community for Nigerian women in the diaspora, addressing their specific needs and concerns.

Proven Solutions

- **Before and After Birth Support:** Comprehensive guidance on supplements, weight control, and overall health.
- **Seamless Birthing Experience:** Practical advice for an "ice cream birth"—a smooth, pleasant, and easy birthing process.
- **Preventing Traumatic Experiences:** Techniques to avoid traumatic childbirth, ensuring a positive experience.
- **Maintaining Physical Shape:** Post-birth strategies to help women retain their best shape and live a healthy life.

The Birth Without Wahala Campaigns has since run four successful cohorts with the fifth one currently ongoing.

This research will be examining the third campaign by conducting an in-depth case study analysis of how the campaign works.

This case study method allows for a detailed examination of the campaign's objectives and structure, providing context to the effectiveness of PR and content marketing strategies in promoting digital antenatal services.

6.5.5 Typical Week during "Birth without Wahala 3"

The Birthsafe Instagram page maintained a consistent style in line with the platform layout. In the morning was a blue post showcasing testimonials from women who had used the Birthsafe's digital antenatal services to achieve what they call 'A Sweet Ice-cream Birth.' In the afternoon, a white and purple post goes up; this post is strictly UserGeneratedContent for driving engagement. While in the evening engaging and interesting reels are posted either from TikTok or Instagram.

Figure 21: Post arrangement from @birthsafeng on Instagram

During the third iteration of the campaign, the activities were structured to maximize engagement and convert anyone who lands on the Instagram page into joining the program.

Registration for the program began as early as May 6th, 2024, although classes did not begin until May 29th, 2024.

The program was extended from 4weeks and ended on June 16th.

Below are some of the PR and Content marketing strategies seen on the Instagram page.

- **5 Things You Must Track in an Antenatal Scan:**

 birthsafeng ⋮

**5 THINGS YOU
MUST TRACK IN AN
ANTENATAL SCAN**
FOR A SAFE PREGNANCY AND CHILDBIRTH

View Insights Boost Post

Liked by lady_kristiejackson1 and 167 others

birthsafeng Talk true , did you know what you were supposed to be tracking in your antenatal scans?... [more](#)

Figure 22: This was a collaborative post with influencers. Offering a low budget product to upsell the program.

- IG Live (4 Ways to Know If Hypertension Is Affecting Your Pregnancy):

Figure 23: Live Q&A sessions on Instagram, addressing common pregnancy concerns and providing expert advice.

- Leveraging on a viral post on pain

Figure 24: This was a pain post involving a popular celebrity. The post was followed by an IG live offering insights to how to avoid such happening to the women. The Instagram page recorded a higher engagement rate than other days which also led to more people registering for the Birth Without Wahala Program.

- **Pregnancy Affirmations**

Figure 25: The women love these pregnancy affirmation posts. It is always guaranteed to get them commenting and affirming. It also led to more people singing up for the program.

- **Interactive Post**

birthsafeng

Let's discuss

Have you ever lost a job or denied a promotion at work just because you're pregnant?

View Insights Boost Post

♥️ 💬 📍 📌

Liked by diaryofanaijacsmum and 303 others

birthsafeng | just heard the most heartbreaking story about this. Do you know anyone it has happened to?... more

View all 84 comments

Figure 26: Post addressing pain points and current realities of pregnant women made them feel more heard, providing a sense of trust in the brand.

- Educational Post

birthsafeng

+BIRTHSAFE

1/8

She Went For Scan And Did Not See The Foetus...

Was there hope?

View Insights

Boost Again

Liked by handpickedbyayinke and 564 others

birthsafeng Awwwww....this is sooooo beautiful!
👍👍👍👍👍👍👍... more

Figure 27: Case study example posts like this often-included useful tips and advice, focusing on practical and actionable information.

- **Cultural barriers and antagonism from the older generation**

Figure 28: Sharing user generated content like these from the women in the community often led to others wanting to join. It portrays a united front and safe space for women against any elements not in support of their achieving a sweet ice-cream birth.

Conclusion: This structured approach supports the Content Marketing Funnel, which suggests that consistent, high-quality content at various stages of engagement can drive user retention and satisfaction (Halligan & Shah, 2009).

6.5.6 Marketing and Promotional Techniques

The campaign employed a variety of marketing techniques, including clickbait style content, user-generated content, influencer collaborations, and interactive social media posts. For example, weekly Instagram Live sessions and interactive posts were used to maintain high engagement levels.

- **User-Generated Content:** The campaign encouraged users to share their pregnancy /childbirth journeys and experiences with Birthsafe's services, fostering a sense of community and trust.
- **Influencer Collaborations:** Collaborations with popular figures in the health and wellness industry helped to amplify the campaign's reach and credibility.
- **Interactive Posts:** Polls, Q&A sessions, pregnancy affirmations and live interactions on social media platforms were used to engage users and provide real-time support and information.

These strategies align with the Content Marketing Institute's best practices, which emphasize the importance of user-generated content and influencer partnerships in digital marketing (Pulizzi, 2012).

The focus on marketing and promotional techniques within the case study provides practical examples of how PR and content marketing strategies are implemented, addressing the research question on their effectiveness.

6.5.7 Impact and Outcomes

The campaign was successful in increasing awareness and engagement, with a significant rise in the number of telehealth consultations and online education module completions. User feedback indicated an elevated level of satisfaction with the services provided, although some users still faced connectivity and literacy challenges.

By examining the impact and outcomes of the "Birth Without Wahala" campaign, the case study provides empirical evidence of the success and limitations of PR and content marketing strategies, addressing the research questions and contributing to the overall research aims.

6.5.8 User Feedback and Testimonials

Positive Experiences

Users reported overwhelmingly positive experiences with Birthsafe's digital antenatal services. They appreciated the convenience and quality of information provided, which helped them manage their pregnancies more effectively. Testimonials highlighted the impact on their confidence and knowledge, with many users noting that the services had alleviated their anxiety and provided a sense of security.

Figure 29: These positive experiences align with previous research indicating that digital health interventions can enhance patient satisfaction and health outcomes (Lupton, 2014).

Improved Health Outcomes

Many users reported improved health outcomes, including better management of pregnancy symptoms, increased adherence to medical advice, and reduced anxiety. The availability of remote monitoring and telehealth consultations was particularly praised for providing timely support and intervention.

Figure 30: This correlates with studies that have shown that digital health services can improve health outcomes by providing continuous support and reducing barriers to care (Morrison et al., 2018).

Engagement Metrics

Prominent levels of engagement were recorded, particularly for live sessions and interactive posts. Users appreciated the real-time interaction and support, which made them feel more connected and reassured. Engagement metrics showed a steady increase in the number of active users, positive feedback, and content shares.

Figure 31: Engagement metrics are crucial indicators of the success of digital marketing campaigns and their ability to retain user interest (Brodie et al., 2013).

6.6 Barriers to Adoption

6.6.1 Digital Literacy

Limited digital literacy among users posed a significant challenge. Many users required assistance to navigate digital platforms and access the services. This highlighted the need for more user-friendly interfaces and digital skills training programs.

This confirms previous research which identified digital literacy as a critical barrier to the adoption of digital health services, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (van Deursen & van Dijk, 2014).

6.6.2 Internet Connectivity

Poor internet connectivity, especially in rural areas, hindered access to digital services. Users in these areas faced frequent disruptions and slow internet speeds, which affected their ability to fully benefit from the services.

This finding is consistent with studies that highlight infrastructure challenges as significant barriers to digital health adoption in developing regions (World Bank, 2016).

6.6.3 Cultural and Socioeconomic Barriers

Cultural beliefs and financial constraints also affected the adoption of digital antenatal services. Some users were hesitant to adopt modern technologies due to traditional beliefs and practices. Additionally, the cost of internet access and digital devices was a barrier for low-income users.

These barriers are well-documented in the literature, with cultural and socioeconomic factors often limiting the reach and effectiveness of digital health interventions (Gurman et al., 2012).

6.7 Tying Findings to Research Objectives and Questions

6.7.1 Research Objective 1: Evaluate the Awareness and Usage of Digital Antenatal Services

The findings revealed a prominent level of awareness (75%) but a lower usage rate (60%), indicating a gap between knowledge and action. This aligns with Research Question 1, which sought to understand the awareness and usage of digital antenatal services among women in Nigeria.

6.7.2 Research Objective 2: Identify the Perceived Benefits and Challenges

The survey and interviews identified key benefits such as convenience, accessibility, and comprehensive information. Challenges included digital literacy, internet access, and cultural barriers. This addresses Research Question 2, which aimed to identify the perceived benefits and challenges of using digital antenatal services.

6.7.3 Research Objective 3: Assess the Effectiveness of PR and Content Marketing Strategies

The case study of the "Birth without Wahala" campaigns showed that PR and content marketing strategies effectively increased engagement and user satisfaction. This finding responds to Research Question 3, which focused on assessing the effectiveness of these strategies.

6.7.4 Research Objective 4: Explore User Feedback and Testimonials

Positive user feedback and testimonials highlighted the impact of Birthsafe's services on maternal health outcomes, supporting Research Question 4, which aimed to explore user experiences and perceptions.

Chapter 7: Discussion and Analysis of Research Findings

This chapter discusses the findings of the study on the effectiveness of PR and content marketing strategies used by Birthsafe Nigeria to promote digital antenatal care services. The findings are integrated with the theoretical frameworks and previous research discussed in the literature review to provide a comprehensive understanding of how these strategies align with or diverge from existing theories and practices in PR content marketing and healthcare.

7.1 Strategic Goals and Motivations

The primary strategic goal of Birthsafe Nigeria, as identified by Dr. Umoette, was to enhance the accessibility and reliability of antenatal care for women, particularly in rural areas. This goal resonates with the accessibility framework highlighted by Laranjo et al. (2015), which underscores the critical role of accessibility in digital health services. Van Deursen and van Dijk (2014) also emphasize the importance of overcoming geographical barriers to healthcare access.

By focusing on digital antenatal care, Birthsafe Nigeria addresses a critical gap in healthcare delivery. This approach aligns with Lupton's (2014) analysis, which suggests that digital health technologies can bridge significant gaps in care, enhancing access and outcomes. The emphasis on reliability reflects the findings of Morrison et al. (2018), who noted the importance of trust and dependability in healthcare services. Birthsafe's strategy to ensure reliability through consistent and high-quality digital services is crucial for building trust among their target audience, which is essential in a context where traditional healthcare services might be perceived as unreliable.

Furthermore, Birthsafe's goal to make antenatal care more accessible aligns with the Health Belief Model (HBM), which posits that individuals are more likely to engage in health-promoting behaviors if they perceive the benefits of taking action (Rosenstock, 1974). By providing accessible and reliable digital antenatal care, Birthsafe addresses perceived barriers and enhances perceived benefits, encouraging greater uptake of these services.

7.2 Design and Implementation of PR and Content Marketing Strategies

Birthsafe employed a comprehensive approach to PR and content marketing, utilizing social media campaigns, influencer partnerships, and user-generated content. These strategies align with Tuten and Solomon's (2017) findings that interactive posts and testimonials can significantly enhance audience engagement and build trust.

The use of data-driven strategies to refine content and PR efforts is supported by Kaplan and Haenlein (2010), who highlight the importance of analytics in optimizing digital marketing efforts. Birthsafe's analysis of engagement metrics and user feedback allowed them to tailor their content more effectively, ensuring it resonated with their audience. This iterative approach to content marketing aligns with the principles of agile marketing, which emphasizes continuous improvement based on real-time data (Holliman & Rowley, 2014).

The incorporation of influencer partnerships and user-generated content further amplifies Birthsafe's message, leveraging the credibility and reach of influencers to engage a broader audience. This strategy is consistent with Ashley and Tuten's (2015) findings, which indicate that influencers and authentic user experiences can significantly enhance the credibility and reach of digital marketing campaigns. Birthsafe's success in this area demonstrates the effectiveness of leveraging social proof and third-party endorsements to build trust and encourage engagement.

Moreover, the use of social media as a primary channel for PR and content marketing reflects the theories of media richness and social presence (Daft & Lengel, 1986). Social media platforms offer rich, interactive environments that facilitate two-way communication and enhance the sense of social presence, making them ideal for engaging with audiences and fostering community around digital antenatal care services.

7.3 Challenges and Obstacles

Several challenges were identified, including low digital literacy, limited internet access, and cultural resistance to digital healthcare solutions. These challenges are well-documented in the literature. Van Deursen and van Dijk (2014) highlight digital literacy as a critical barrier to digital health adoption, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. Similarly, the World Bank (2016) underscores infrastructure limitations as a significant hurdle in the delivery of digital health services.

Addressing these challenges is essential for the successful implementation of digital health services. Enhancing digital literacy through user-friendly interfaces and training programs is crucial. Van Deursen and van Dijk (2014) suggest that targeted interventions aimed at improving digital skills can significantly enhance the adoption and utilization of digital health services. Birthsafe's efforts in this regard can be guided by these insights, focusing on simplifying the user experience and providing educational resources to improve digital literacy among their target audience.

Cultural and socioeconomic barriers also play a significant role in the adoption of digital health services. Gurman et al. (2012) discusses how traditional beliefs, and financial constraints can limit the reach and effectiveness of digital health interventions. These barriers must be addressed through culturally sensitive educational campaigns and policies aimed at reducing the financial burden associated with accessing digital health services. Chib et al. (2015) highlights the importance of community engagement and culturally appropriate messaging in overcoming resistance to digital healthcare solutions. Birthsafe's strategy should include engaging with community leaders and influencers to promote the benefits of digital antenatal care in a culturally appropriate manner.

7.4 Effectiveness of PR and Content Marketing Strategies

The "Birth Without Wahala" campaign was particularly effective in increasing engagement and user satisfaction. High levels of trust and positive feedback from users indicate the success of these strategies. Morrison et al. (2018) highlight the potential for digital health interventions to improve health outcomes through enhanced engagement and information access. The positive user feedback aligns with Lupton (2014), who discusses the impact of digital health on user perceptions and health outcomes.

The success of the campaign can also be attributed to the principles of relationship management theory, which emphasizes the importance of building and maintaining relationships with key publics (Ledingham & Bruning, 1998). Birthsafe's use of testimonials, interactive content, and influencer partnerships helped to foster strong relationships with their audience, enhancing trust and encouraging ongoing engagement. This relational approach is supported by the findings of Grunig and Huang (2000), who highlight the importance of trust, satisfaction, and commitment in effective public relations.

Pulizzi (2012) and Ashley and Tuten (2015) also support the role of well-crafted content marketing in boosting user engagement and satisfaction. Birthsafe's strategic use of diverse content formats and channels has proven effective in reaching and engaging their target audience. The positive reception of these strategies indicates that they are well-aligned with best practices in digital health communication and content marketing.

Moreover, the use of social media as a primary channel for PR and content marketing aligns with Kaplan and Haenlein's (2010) findings on the effectiveness of social media in engaging diverse audiences. Birthsafe's success in leveraging social media platforms underscores the importance of these channels in modern PR and content marketing strategies, particularly in the context of digital health services.

7.5 Digital Literacy and Internet Connectivity

Limited digital literacy and poor internet connectivity were significant barriers affecting users' ability to benefit from digital services. This finding is consistent with Van Deursen and van Dijk (2014), who identified digital literacy as a major barrier to the adoption of digital health services. The World Bank (2016) highlighted infrastructure challenges, particularly in rural areas, as significant impediments to effective digital health service delivery.

Enhancing digital literacy through user-friendly interfaces and training programs is essential in mitigating this barrier. Van Deursen and van Dijk (2014) suggest that targeted interventions aimed at improving digital skills can significantly enhance the adoption and utilization of digital health services. Birthsafe can implement these recommendations by designing intuitive user interfaces and providing educational resources to improve digital literacy among their target audience.

Improving internet infrastructure in rural areas is also critical to addressing connectivity issues. The World Bank (2016) emphasizes the need for investment in digital infrastructure to support the effective delivery of digital health services. Birthsafe can advocate for better internet infrastructure and explore partnerships with technology providers to enhance connectivity in underserved areas. This approach aligns with the recommendations of the Broadband Commission for Sustainable Development (2019), which highlights the importance of public-private partnerships in expanding digital infrastructure and improving access to digital health services.

7.6 Cultural and Socioeconomic Barriers

Cultural beliefs and financial constraints were major barriers to the adoption of digital antenatal services. These barriers are well-documented in the literature. Gurman et al. (2012) discusses how cultural and socioeconomic factors limit the reach and effectiveness of digital health interventions. The research by Chib et al. (2015) and van Deursen and van Dijk (2014) further supports the finding

that without addressing these fundamental issues, digital health services cannot achieve their full potential.

Developing culturally sensitive educational campaigns is crucial in overcoming resistance to digital healthcare solutions. Birthsafe can engage with community leaders and influencers to promote the benefits of digital antenatal care in a culturally appropriate manner. Additionally, exploring subsidized or low-cost options for internet access and digital devices is necessary to address financial constraints and ensure broader access to digital health services.

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) can provide a useful framework for understanding and addressing these barriers. TPB posits that individuals' intentions to engage in a behavior are influenced by their attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control (Ajzen, 1991). Birthsafe's educational campaigns can aim to positively influence these factors by providing information that enhances positive attitudes towards digital antenatal care, leveraging social norms by involving community influencers, and increasing perceived behavioral control by offering support and resources to improve digital literacy and access.

Chapter 8: Strategic Recommendations

8.1 Introduction

This chapter presents detailed strategic recommendations aimed at enhancing the adoption and effectiveness of digital antenatal services in Nigeria, particularly focusing on Birthsafe Nigeria. The recommendations are drawn from the research findings and are aligned with the objectives and goals outlined in the earlier chapters. They aim to address the barriers identified and leverage opportunities to improve maternal health outcomes.

8.2 Enhancing Digital Literacy and Internet Connectivity

One of the primary barriers identified is the lack of digital literacy among expectant mothers, especially in rural areas. To address this, Birthsafe Nigeria should consider several targeted strategies:

Community-Based Training Programs:

- **Implementation:** Collaborate with local health workers and NGOs to establish training programs that educate women on using digital tools for antenatal care. These programs can be integrated into existing community health outreach initiatives.
- **Content:** Develop easy-to-understand materials and hands-on training sessions that cover basic smartphone usage, internet navigation, and accessing digital health services.
- **Sustainability:** Train local women as digital literacy ambassadors to ensure the continuity of these programs and create a peer-support network.

Partnerships with Telecom Providers:

- **Subsidized Data Packages:** Collaborate with telecom companies to offer subsidized or free data packages specifically for accessing digital antenatal services. This initiative can be marketed as part of corporate social responsibility (CSR) programs.
- **Free Access Zones:** Establish free Wi-Fi zones in key community centers, such as health clinics and markets, where women can access digital antenatal services without incurring data costs.

Digital Literacy Campaigns:

- **Mass Media Campaigns:** Launch mass media campaigns using radio, television, and social media to raise awareness about the importance of digital literacy and available antenatal services.
- **Incentives:** Offer incentives such as free mobile data or discounts on health products to encourage participation in digital literacy programs.

8.3 Addressing Cultural and Socioeconomic Barriers

Cultural beliefs and socioeconomic factors significantly influence the adoption of digital health services. To mitigate these barriers, Birthsafe Nigeria should implement the following strategies:

Culturally Sensitive Content:

- **Content Development:** Involve local leaders, influencers, and healthcare professionals in creating content that respects and integrates cultural beliefs and practices. This approach will enhance the acceptability and relevance of the content.
-
- **Localization:** Translate materials into local languages and use culturally relevant examples and analogies to make the information more relatable.

Community Engagement:

- **Engagement Programs:** Organize community meetings and workshops to discuss the benefits of digital antenatal services and address any cultural concerns. Use these platforms to share success stories and testimonials from local women.
- **Influencer Partnerships:** Collaborate with respected community figures, including religious leaders and traditional birth attendants, to endorse and promote digital antenatal services.

Affordable Service Options:

- **Sliding Scale Fees:** Introduce a sliding scale fee structure based on income levels, ensuring that services are affordable for all women regardless of their financial situation.

- **Payment Plans:** Offer flexible payment plans that allow women to pay for services in installments, reducing the financial burden.

Financial Support Programs:

- **Subsidies and Grants:** Seek government and NGO subsidies to reduce the cost of services for low-income women. Apply for grants to fund outreach programs and digital literacy initiatives.
- **Microfinance Options:** Partner with microfinance institutions to provide small loans to women for purchasing smartphones or paying for digital health services.

8.4 Strengthening PR and Content Marketing Strategies

Effective PR and content marketing are crucial for increasing awareness and engagement. Recommendations include:

Authentic Storytelling:

- **User Testimonials:** Continue to use real-life stories and testimonials from users who have benefited from Birthsafe Nigeria's services. Highlighting individual experiences can build trust and relatability.
- **Visual Content:** Utilize high-quality images and videos of real users, healthcare professionals, and community events to create an emotional connection with the audience.

Interactive Content:

- **Live Sessions:** Enhance engagement through live sessions, Q&A forums, and interactive webinars that allow real-time interaction between healthcare providers and users. These sessions can cover diverse topics, including prenatal care, nutrition, and childbirth preparation.
- **Social Media Campaigns:** Run interactive campaigns on social media platforms, encouraging users to share their experiences, ask questions, and participate in discussions.

Data-Driven Marketing:

- **Analytics Utilization:** Utilize social media analytics and user feedback to tailor content and marketing strategies. This data-driven approach ensures that the content remains relevant, engaging, and impactful.
- **Targeted Campaigns:** Develop targeted marketing campaigns based on user demographics, preferences, and behavior. Use segmentation to deliver personalized content that resonates with different audience groups.

Collaborations and Partnerships:

- **Influencer Collaborations:** Partner with social media influencers, bloggers, and celebrities who can amplify the reach of the campaign and attract a broader audience.
- **Corporate Partnerships:** Collaborate with companies and brands that align with Birthsafe Nigeria's mission. Joint campaigns and sponsorships can provide additional resources and increase visibility.

8.5 Expanding Outreach to Rural Areas

To reach women who are not online, especially in rural areas, Birthsafe Nigeria should consider:

Mobile Outreach Clinics:

- **Implementation:** Establish mobile clinics that travel to remote and underserved areas, providing both digital and in-person antenatal services. These clinics can serve as access points for digital platforms and offer hands-on support and education.
- **Services Offered:** Provide comprehensive antenatal care services, including health screenings, education sessions, and digital literacy training.

Local Partnerships:

- **Community Health Workers:** Partner with community health workers and local organizations to spread awareness about digital antenatal services and facilitate

their use. These workers can act as intermediaries, helping women navigate digital platforms.

- **NGO Collaboration:** Collaborate with NGOs that focus on maternal health and rural development to extend the reach of digital antenatal services.

Offline Engagement:

- **Print Materials:** Develop print materials such as brochures, posters, and leaflets that provide information about digital antenatal services and how to access them. Distribute these materials in community centers, health clinics, and markets.
- **Radio Programs:** Use local radio stations to broadcast educational programs and advertisements about digital antenatal services, targeting women who may not have internet access.

Incentive Programs:

- **Referral Programs:** Implement referral programs that encourage current users to refer friends and family members. Offer incentives such as discounts or free services for successful referrals.
- **Participation Rewards:** Provide rewards for participating in digital literacy training or attending antenatal care sessions, such as free health products or services.

8.6 Government and Policy Advocacy

Engaging with government bodies and influencing policy can create a supportive environment for digital health initiatives. Key recommendations include:

Policy Advocacy:

- **Health Policy Engagement:** Advocate for policies that support digital health innovations, including funding for digital literacy programs and incentives for healthcare providers to adopt digital tools.
- **Legislative Support:** Work with lawmakers to draft and implement legislation that promotes the use of digital health services, ensuring that they are integrated into the national healthcare system.

Government Collaborations:

- **Pilot Programs:** Collaborate with state and local governments to pilot and scale successful digital antenatal programs. Leverage public resources and infrastructure to expand reach and impact.
- **Public-Private Partnerships:** Form public-private partnerships to combine resources and expertise from both sectors. These partnerships can enhance service delivery and sustainability.

Funding and Grants:

- **Government Grants:** Apply for government grants to fund digital health initiatives, focusing on projects that improve maternal health outcomes and reduce barriers to access.
- **International Funding:** Seek funding from international organizations and development agencies that support maternal health and digital innovation.

Awareness Campaigns:

- **Public Awareness:** Launch public awareness campaigns in collaboration with government agencies to educate the population about the benefits of digital antenatal services. These campaigns can include mass media advertisements, community events, and public service announcements.
- **Health Worker Training:** Advocate for the inclusion of digital health training in the curriculum for healthcare workers. This training will ensure that healthcare providers are equipped to support and promote digital antenatal services.

8.7 Leveraging Technology and Innovation

Technological advancements can significantly enhance the delivery and effectiveness of digital antenatal services. Recommendations include:

Mobile Health Applications:

- **App Development:** Invest in the development of user-friendly mobile health applications that provide comprehensive antenatal care information, appointment scheduling, and virtual consultations.

- **Features:** Incorporate features such as reminders for prenatal check-ups, nutrition advice, and emergency contacts. Ensure that the app is available in multiple languages and accessible to women with varying levels of digital literacy. (NB: Birthsafe is already working on a handy 24/7 digital app in line with this recommendation)

Telehealth Services:

- **Virtual Consultations:** Expand telehealth services to include virtual consultations with healthcare providers. This service can be particularly beneficial for women in remote areas who have limited access to healthcare facilities.
- **24/7 Support:** Offer 24/7 support through telehealth platforms, allowing women to seek advice and assistance at any time.

Data Analytics and AI:

- **Predictive Analytics:** Utilize data analytics and artificial intelligence to identify trends, predict potential health issues, and personalize care plans for expectant mothers.
- **Monitoring and Feedback:** Implement systems for continuous monitoring and feedback to improve service delivery and user experience.

Innovative Outreach Methods:

- **SMS and Voice Messages:** Use SMS and voice message services to deliver health information and reminders to women who may not have access to smartphones or the internet. This method ensures that essential information reaches a broader audience.
- **Community Kiosks:** Set up digital kiosks in community centers where women can access antenatal care information and services. These kiosks can be staffed by trained personnel to assist users.

8.8 Monitoring and Evaluation

To ensure the effectiveness of these strategies, it is crucial to implement a robust monitoring and evaluation framework:

Performance Metrics:

- **Key Indicators:** Define key performance indicators (KPIs) to measure the success of digital antenatal services, such as user engagement, satisfaction levels, and health outcomes.
- **Data Collection:** Collect and analyze data regularly to assess the impact of the implemented strategies and identify areas for improvement.

User Feedback:

- **Surveys and Interviews:** Conduct regular surveys and interviews with users to gather feedback on their experiences and suggestions for improvement.
- **Focus Groups:** Organize focus groups to gain deeper insights into user needs and preferences, allowing for more targeted and effective interventions.

Continuous Improvement:

- **Iterative Process:** Use the findings from monitoring and evaluation to refine and improve strategies continuously. This iterative process ensures that the services remain relevant and effective.
- **Stakeholder Involvement:** Involve stakeholders, including users, healthcare providers, and community leaders, in the evaluation process to gain diverse perspectives and foster collaboration.

Conclusion

The strategic recommendations outlined in this chapter are designed to address the barriers to the adoption and effectiveness of digital antenatal services in Nigeria. By enhancing digital literacy, addressing cultural and socioeconomic barriers, strengthening PR and content marketing strategies, expanding outreach to rural areas, engaging with government bodies, leveraging technology and innovation, and implementing robust monitoring and evaluation processes, Birthsafe Nigeria can significantly improve maternal health outcomes and ensure that more women have access to high-quality antenatal care.

Chapter 9: Conclusion and Future Research

9.1 Introduction

This concluding chapter summarizes the key findings of the research, reiterates the strategic recommendations proposed, and outlines directions for future research. The goal is to provide a comprehensive overview of how digital antenatal services, such as those offered by Birthsafe Nigeria, can be optimized to improve maternal health outcomes in Nigeria. This chapter also emphasizes the importance of continuous evaluation and adaptation to meet the evolving needs of expectant mothers.

9.2 Summary of Findings

The research conducted through in-depth interviews, surveys, and case study analysis of the "Birth Without Wahala" campaign has provided valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities associated with promoting digital antenatal services. Key findings are summarized as follows:

Motivations and Vision:

- Birthsafe Nigeria was inspired by the need to address the high maternal mortality rate in Nigeria and to leverage digital technology to provide accessible antenatal care.
- The vision is to ensure that every expectant mother, regardless of her location or socioeconomic status, has access to quality antenatal care.

PR and Content Marketing Strategies:

- The strategies involve authentic storytelling, interactive content, data-driven marketing, and collaborations with influencers and corporate partners.
- These strategies are designed to raise awareness, build trust, and engage the target audience effectively.

Challenges in Promoting Digital Antenatal Services:

- **Digital Literacy:** A significant barrier is the lack of digital literacy among expectant mothers, particularly in rural areas.
- **Internet Connectivity:** Limited access to reliable internet and high data costs hinders the adoption of digital services.
- **Cultural Beliefs:** Traditional beliefs and skepticism towards digital health services pose challenges.
- **Socioeconomic Factors:** Financial constraints prevent many women from accessing digital antenatal services, as they cannot afford smartphones or data costs.
- **Rural Access:** Many women in rural areas are not online and thus remain unaware of the available digital services.

Survey Findings:

- **Awareness and Usage:** The survey revealed that a significant percentage of expectant mothers are unaware of digital antenatal services. Among those aware, usage is lower in rural areas compared to urban areas.
- **Perceived Benefits:** Respondents who use digital antenatal services reported benefits such as convenience, timely information, and the ability to access expert advice.
- **Barriers to Usage:** Key barriers identified include lack of digital literacy, high data costs, and cultural resistance to non-traditional forms of antenatal care.

Case Study Analysis: Birth Without Wahala Campaign:

- The campaign, which included endorsements, live sessions, and various forms of interactive content, significantly increased engagement on social media.
- Metrics such as likes, comments, and shares demonstrated an elevated level of user engagement. The campaign also resulted in a notable increase in followers and awareness about Birthsafe Nigeria.
- The use of clickbait content and visual consistency in the campaign materials effectively captured and retained user attention.

9.3 Strategic Recommendations

Based on the findings, several strategic recommendations were proposed to enhance the adoption and effectiveness of digital antenatal services:

Enhancing Digital Literacy and Internet Connectivity:

- Community-based training programs, partnerships with telecom providers, and digital literacy campaigns are essential to improve digital skills and internet access.

Addressing Cultural and Socioeconomic Barriers:

- Developing culturally sensitive content, engaging with community leaders, offering affordable service options, and providing financial support can mitigate these barriers.

Strengthening PR and Content Marketing Strategies:

- Focusing on authentic storytelling, interactive content, data-driven marketing, and collaborations can increase awareness and engagement.

Expanding Outreach to Rural Areas:

- Establishing mobile outreach clinics, partnering with local organizations, using print materials and radio programs, and implementing incentive programs can reach women in rural areas.

Government and Policy Advocacy:

- Engaging with government bodies, advocating for supportive policies, forming public-private partnerships, and securing funding and grants are crucial for sustainability.

Leveraging Technology and Innovation:

- Investing in mobile health applications, expanding telehealth services, utilizing data analytics and AI, and adopting innovative outreach methods can enhance service delivery.

Monitoring and Evaluation:

- Implementing a robust monitoring and evaluation framework with performance metrics, user feedback, and continuous improvement processes ensures the effectiveness of strategies.

9.4 Contributions to Literature

This research contributes to the existing literature on digital health services and maternal health by providing an in-depth case study of Birthsafe Nigeria. The study highlights the unique challenges and opportunities in the Nigerian context and offers practical strategies for improving digital antenatal care. The findings underscore the importance of a multi-faceted approach that addresses technological, cultural, and socioeconomic factors.

9.5 Implications for Practice

The insights and recommendations from this research have significant implications for practice:

Healthcare Providers:

- Healthcare providers can leverage the strategies outlined to enhance their digital antenatal services, ensuring they are accessible, acceptable, and effective for all women, especially those in underserved areas.

Policymakers:

- Policymakers can use the findings to develop supportive policies and programs that promote digital health innovations and address barriers to access.

NGOs and Community Organizations:

- NGOs and community organizations can implement community-based initiatives and partnerships that support digital literacy, internet access, and maternal health education.

Telecom and Tech Companies:

- Telecom and tech companies can collaborate with health organizations to provide affordable data packages and develop user-friendly health applications tailored to the needs of expectant mothers.

9.6 Limitations of the Study

While this research provides valuable insights, it is important to acknowledge its limitations:

Scope:

The study focuses primarily on Birthsafe Nigeria and may not fully capture the diverse experiences and challenges faced by other organizations offering digital antenatal services in different regions of Nigeria.

Sample Size: The in-depth interviews were conducted with a limited number of participants. A larger sample size could provide more comprehensive data and insights.

Generalisability: The findings may not be generalisable to other countries or contexts with diverse cultural, socioeconomic, and technological landscapes.

Temporal Context: The research reflects the situation at the time of the study. Changes in technology, policy, and socioeconomic conditions may affect the relevance of the findings and recommendations.

9.7 Recommendations for Future Research

Future research should build on this study to further explore and address the challenges of promoting digital antenatal services. Key areas for future research include:

Broader Geographic Scope:

- Conducting similar studies in different regions of Nigeria and other countries to compare experiences and strategies. This can help identify context-specific barriers and opportunities.

Longitudinal Studies:

- Implementing longitudinal studies to assess the long-term impact of digital antenatal services on maternal health outcomes. Such studies can provide insights into the sustainability and effectiveness of different strategies over time.

Comparative Analysis:

- Comparing the effectiveness of various digital health platforms and applications in delivering antenatal care. This analysis can identify best practices and inform the development of more effective digital tools.

Interdisciplinary Approaches:

- Combining perspectives from public health, technology, sociology, and economics to develop holistic strategies that address the multifaceted challenges of digital health adoption.

User-Centered Design:

- Conducting research that involves users in the design and evaluation of digital health services. User-centered design can ensure that the services meet the needs and preferences of expectant mothers, leading to higher adoption rates.

Policy Impact Assessment:

- Assessing the impact of government policies and programs on the adoption and effectiveness of digital antenatal services. This research can provide evidence to support policy advocacy and development.

9.8 Concluding Remarks

This research has highlighted the critical role of digital antenatal services in improving maternal health outcomes in Nigeria. By addressing the barriers to adoption and leveraging the opportunities identified, Birthsafe Nigeria and similar organizations can significantly enhance the accessibility, acceptability, and effectiveness of their services. The strategic recommendations provided offer a comprehensive roadmap for overcoming challenges and ensuring that all expectant mothers, regardless of their location or socioeconomic status, have access to quality antenatal care.

The journey towards optimizing digital antenatal services is ongoing, and continuous evaluation and adaptation are essential. Future research and practice should remain focused on understanding and addressing the evolving needs of expectant mothers, ensuring that digital health innovations contribute to better health outcomes and a brighter future for all.

The successful implementation of these strategies requires collaboration among healthcare providers, policymakers, community organizations, telecom and tech companies, and the broader community. By working together, we can create a supportive environment that empowers women with the knowledge, tools, and resources they need for a healthy pregnancy and safe childbirth.

Reference list

Adedokun, S.T. and Yaya, S. 2020. Correlates of antenatal care utilization among women of reproductive age in sub-Saharan Africa: evidence from multinomial analysis of demographic and health surveys (2010–2018) from 31 countries. *Archives of public health* 78(1). Available at: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s13690-020-00516-w> [Accessed: 29 May 2024].

Adewuyi, E.O., Zhao, Y., Auta, A. and Lamichhane, R. 2017. Prevalence and factors associated with non-utilization of healthcare facility for childbirth in rural and urban Nigeria: Analysis of a national population-based survey. *Scandinavian Journal of Public Health* 45(6), pp. 675–682. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1403494817705562>.

Aniefiok Udonquak. 2024. *Technology, proactive care can reverse high maternal mortality numbers - BirthSafe founder - Businessday NG*. Available at: <https://businessday.ng/health/article/technology-proactive-care-can-reverse-high-maternal-mortality-numbers-birthsafe-founder/> [Accessed: 16 June 2024].

Bankole, I. 2022. *Nigeria has a Maternal Health problem*. Available at: <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2022/09/nigeria-has-a-maternal-health-problem/> [Accessed: 29 June 2024].

Bassey Ebenso et al. 2021. What Are the Contextual Enablers and Impacts of Using Digital Technology to Extend Maternal and Child Health Services to Rural Areas? Findings of a Qualitative Study from Nigeria. *Frontiers in Global Women s Health* 2. Available at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/global-womens-health/articles/10.3389/fgwh.2021.670494/full> [Accessed: 13 August 2024].

Birthsafe NG. 2023. *About us*. Available at: <https://birthsafeng.com/> [Accessed: 16 June 2024].

BirthSafe Nigeria | Pregnancy & Childbirth, Motherhood (@birthsafeng) • Instagram photos and videos. 2020. Available at: <https://www.instagram.com/birthsafeng/?hl=en> [Accessed: 16 June 2024].

Carrie Lewis Miller and Manderfeld, M. 2021. *Theory of Planned Behavior*. Available at: <https://mlpp.pressbooks.pub/mavlearn/chapter/theory-of-planned-behavior/> [Accessed: 15 August 2024].

Downey, A. 2020. *Video consultations to apps - how digital tools can transform maternity care*. Available at: <https://www.digitalhealth.net/2020/08/video-consultations-to-apps-how-digital-tools-can-transform-maternity-care/> [Accessed: 13 August 2024].

Elrod, J.K. and Fortenberry, J.L. 2020. Public relations in health and medicine: using publicity and other unpaid promotional methods to engage audiences. *BMC health services research* 20(S1). Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7491107/> [Accessed: 29 May 2024].

Etuk, I. et al. 2023. Barriers to health in women of reproductive age living with or at risk of non-communicable diseases in Nigeria: a Photovoice study. *BMC women's health* 23(1). Available at: <https://bmcwomenshealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12905-022-02146-6#:~:text=Approximately%20600%2C%20000%20maternal%20deaths,1%20in%204900%20%5B1%5D.> [Accessed: 25 May 2024].

Every Woman Every Child. 2021. Available at: <https://pmnch.who.int/news-and-events/campaigns/every-woman-every-child> [Accessed: 30 June 2024].

Every Woman Every Child | Department of Economic and Social Affairs. 2021. Available at: <https://sdgs.un.org/partnerships/every-woman-every-child> [Accessed: 30 June 2024].

FATUNMOLE, M. and FATUNMOLE, M. 2022. *Four doctors to 10,000 population, Nigeria's highest in two decades - Data | The ICIR- Latest News, Politics, Governance, Elections, Investigation, Factcheck, Covid-19*. Available at: <https://www.icirnigeria.org/four-doctors-to-10000-population-nigerias-highest-in-two-decades-data/> [Accessed: 18 June 2024].

- Geiger, A. 2019. *Share of U.S. adults using social media, including Facebook, is mostly unchanged since 2018*. Available at: <https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2019/04/10/share-of-u-s-adults-using-social-media-including-facebook-is-mostly-unchanged-since-2018/> [Accessed: 29 May 2024].
- Grunig, J.E. and Hunt, T. 1984. *Managing public relations*. New York: Holt, Rinehart, and Winston. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/James-Grunig/publication/322802009_Managing_Public_Relations/links/5a70b327a6fdcc33daa9dfad/Managing-Public-Relations.pdf.
- Honeycutt, E.D. and Paul, K.E. 2004. An Analysis of Health Marketing Quarterly 1991–2002. *Health Marketing Quarterly* 21(4), pp. 77–87. doi: https://doi.org/10.1300/j026v21n04_05.
- Hussein, J., Hirose, A., Owolabi, O., Imamura, M., Lovney Kanguru and Friday Okonofua. 2016. Maternal death and obstetric care audits in Nigeria: a systematic review of barriers and enabling factors in the provision of emergency care. *Reproductive health* 13(1). Available at: <https://reproductive-health-journal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12978-016-0158-4> [Accessed: 31 May 2024].
- Idara, D. 2024. *There are factors you can control to reduce the risk of complications in childbirth such as paralysis*. Available at: <https://www.instagram.com/reel/C77co65uWGR/> [Accessed: 16 June 2024].
- Jakub Babkins. 2023. *Affiliate Marketing Business Plan*. Available at: <https://www.ogscapital.com/article/affiliate-marketing-business-plan> [Accessed: 15 August 2024].
- Lankester, T. and Grills, N.J. 2019. *Setting Up Community Health and Development Programmes in Low and Middle Income Settings*. Oxford University Press. Available at: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241549912> [Accessed: 2 June 2024].
- Lorin, V. 2019. The impact of marketing strategies in healthcare systems. *Journal of medicine and life* 12(2), pp. 93–96. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6685306/> [Accessed: 29 May 2024].

- Maguire, D. 2018. *Digital Change In Health And Social Care*. Available at:
<https://www.kingsfund.org.uk/insight-and-analysis/reports/digital-change-health-social-care>.
- McNabb, M., Chukwu, E., Ojo, O., Shekhar, N., Gill, C.J., Salami, H. and Jega, F. 2015. Assessment of the Quality of Antenatal Care Services Provided by Health Workers Using a Mobile Phone Decision Support Application in Northern Nigeria: A Pre/Post-Intervention Study. van Ooijen, P. M. A. ed. *PLOS ONE* 10(5), p. e0123940. doi:
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0123940>.
- Mechael, P. et al. 2010. *Barriers and Gaps Affecting mHealth in Low and Middle Income Countries: Policy White Paper*. Available at:
https://www.mobileactive.org/pdfs/mHealth_Barriers_White_Paper.pdf.
- Musa Abubakar Kana, Henry Victor Doctor, Bárbara Peleteiro, Nuno Lunet and Barros, H. 2015. Maternal and child health interventions in Nigeria: a systematic review of published studies from 1990 to 2014. *BMC public health* 15(1). Available at:
<https://bmcpublichealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12889-015-1688-3> [Accessed: 29 May 2024].
- Nadezhda Lebedeva, Osipova, K., and Liubov Cherkasova. 2012. Values and Social Capital as Predictors of Attitudes Towards Innovation. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. Available at:
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2084747 [Accessed: 15 August 2024].
- Niran Adetoro and Benedict. 2021. Technology Use for Reproductive Health Information Dissemination to Pregnant Patients in Government Hospitals as Perceived by Midwives in Ogun-State. *Journal of hospital librarianship* 21(2), pp. 184–197. doi:
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15323269.2021.1904187>.
- Olawale Olonade, Olawande, T.I., Oluwatobi Joseph Alabi and Imhonopi, D. 2019. Maternal Mortality and Maternal Health Care in Nigeria: Implications for Socio-Economic Development. *Open Access Macedonian Journal of Medical Sciences* 7(5), pp. 849–855. Available at:
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6447322/> [Accessed: 31 May 2024].

ONWUDIEGWU, U. 1997. The effect of a depressed economy on the utilisation of maternal health services: the Nigerian experience II. *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology* 17(2), pp. 143–148. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01443619750113672>.

Patchanee Malikhao. 2020. Health Communication: Approaches, Strategies, and Ways to Sustainability on Health or Health for All. *Springer eBooks*, pp. 1015–1037. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7278262/> [Accessed: 29 May 2024].

Pulizzi, J. and Rose, R. 2011. *Managing content marketing the real-world guide for creating passionate subscribers to your brand*. Cleveland Ohio McGraw-Hill Education.

Shah, A.M., Zahoor, S.Z. and Qureshi, I.H. 2019. Social Media and Purchasing Behavior: A Study of the Mediating Effect of Customer Relationships. *Journal of Global Marketing* 32(2), pp. 93–115. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08911762.2018.1497243>.

Statista. 2022. *Nigeria: literacy rate, by zone and gender* | Statista. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1124745/literacy-rate-in-nigeria-by-zone-and-gender/> [Accessed: 30 June 2024].

TechCabal. 2023. “Ice-cream births” are saving women’s lives in Nigeria. Available at: <https://techcabal.com/2023/09/18/ice-cream-births-are-saving-womens-lives-in-nigeria/> [Accessed: 16 June 2024].

Tulip. 2022. *Miscarriage: “I was in pain and they did not listen.”* Available at: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/health-60243152> [Accessed: 18 June 2024].

Wakefield, M.A., Loken, B. and Hornik, R.C. 2010. Use of mass media campaigns to change health behaviour. *Lancet* 376(9748), pp. 1261–1271. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20933263/> [Accessed: 29 May 2024].

WHO. 2019. *Maternal health in Nigeria: generating information for action*. Available at: <https://www.who.int/news/item/25-06-2019-maternal-health-in-nigeria-generating-information-for-action> [Accessed: 13 August 2024].

World Health Organization. 2023. *Analytical Fact Sheet Maternal mortality: The urgency of a systemic and multisectoral approach in mitigating maternal deaths in Africa Rationale*.

Available at:

https://files.aho.afro.who.int/afahobckpcontainer/production/files/iAHO_Maternal_Mortality_Regional_Factsheet.pdf.

Yang, H.-D., Lee, J., Park, C. Iwoo and Lee, K. 2014. The Adoption of Mobile Self-Service Technologies: Effects of Availability in Alternative Media and Trust on the Relative Importance of Perceived Usefulness and Ease of Use. *International Journal of Smart Home* 8(4), pp. 165–178. doi: <https://doi.org/10.14257/ijsh.2014.8.4.15>.

Zhang, S. 2024. *A CASE STUDY OF TENCENT'S MOBILE PAYMENT INTERNATIONAL EXPANSION BASED ON DIFFUSION OF INNOVATIONS THEORY*. Available at: <https://conference.stamford.edu/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/13.pdf>. [Accessed: 15 August 2024].